

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D8.2 Summary of Bi-monthly reports-update month 36

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Project

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Executive Summary

The COVINFORM project has implemented a multidisciplinary and intersectional approach to examine how vulnerability is defined and addressed in COVID-19 responses from government, public health, and communication perspectives. The project has examined the impact that different national, regional, and local responses have had on vulnerable and marginalized groups and view these impacts through an intersectional perspective to understand how different factors interconnect, potentially further increasing vulnerability and marginalization.

In line with the objectives of the project, this report aims to provide an overview of the activities implemented within WP8 “Development of solutions, guidelines and recommendations” and in particular within task 8.1 devoted to “Develop and publish bi-monthly reports for different target groups” during the last 18 months of the project. The deliverable is organised as follow: in the first section a synthesis of the objectives and of the content of the bi-monthly reports number 9 to 18 published within task 8.1 is provided. In the second section the content of the published bi-monthly report is presented. Finally, we draft the conclusions.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable aims to present the work conducted within Task 8.1, under WP8, during the last 18 months of the COVINFORM project. WP8, coordinated by the Sapienza University of Rome (SAPIENZA) team, aims to create reports and materials for stakeholders and to develop recommendations and best practices to influence adherence to behavioural advice across different groups in society. In particular, the objective of task 8.1, coordinated by the same team, is to create and publish useful output of the project every two months in the form of brief reports, snippets, webinars, etc. for the different stakeholders. The task started in month 3 of the project, with the first report published in January 2021, and will end with the end of the project, with the last report published in October 2023.

A total of 18 bi-monthly reports were published during the project, more specifically 10 bi-monthly reports in the second half of the project: 8 in brochure format and 2 in video format. In deciding the different topics of the reports, we tried to follow both the development of the pandemic, focusing on topics connected to the crisis, and the evolution of the project, focusing on the findings coming from the activities and analysis conducted in the various WPs. An overview of the reports is presented in Table 1. The full reports are available in the section 2 of the deliverable and on the project website. The authors of the different reports vary depending on the topics covered (Table 1). The reports containing the results of the project's activities were written, under the supervision of the SAPIENZA team, directly by the COVINFORM partners leading the activities. All the reports have been published on the project website¹ and disseminated via the social media channels of the project. Lastly, the reports in video format have been published on the YouTube channel of the project.

The first report (bi-monthly report 9, May 2022) published in the second half of the project is a video interview realized with two practitioners taking part in the project and it collected their stories and insights after two years of the beginning of the pandemic. It is the second part of the videos with practitioners introduced in the eighth report, published in March 2022 and entitled "After two years of pandemic". In this second video, Andreea Furtuna from the Romanian Red Cross (SNCR),

Massimo Fantoni from the Catholic University of the Sacred Heart (UCSC) and Itamar Laist from the Magen David Adom in Israel (MDA) describe the challenges they had to face in the various phases of the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing also on lessons learned and best practices that have been developed in the crisis situation related to the pandemic.

¹ Available at: <https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/bi-monthly-reports/>

Table 1. Overview of the bi-monthly reports published from the 19th month to the 36th month of the project

Number	Date of publication	Title	Topics covered	Authors and contributors	Format
9	May 2022	After two years of pandemic: COVINFORM partners talk about the experiences, challenges and lessons learned	Two video stories from two practitioners about the experiences in their work during the pandemic	Fantoni ,M. (UCSC), Furtuna, A. (SNCRR), Laist, I. (MDA)	Video-interviews
10	July 2022	Socio-economic Impact of COVID-19	A short summary of socio-economic consequences of COVID-19, reporting summary of desk research conducted within COVINFORM	Antunes, D. (FS) Miccoli, S. & Ambrosetti, E. (SAPIENZA)	Brochure
11	September 2022	Resilience in the Systems we live in: 10 European case studies	Overview of the 10 COVINFORM's case studies which aim to identify vulnerability and protective factors of both vulnerable populations and the systems they are a part of, across different geographical settings:	Love, P., & Ricoca-Peixoto, M. (FS)	Brochure
12	November 2022	A civil society organisation perspective on vulnerability: Lesson learned during COVID-19	Lessons learned by civil society organisations (CSOs) about vulnerability during the COVID-19 pandemic: based on qualitative interviews conducted with CSO representatives.	Edward J. (SINUS)	Brochure
13	January 2023	'Closer to death': thinking about dying in pandemic times	This bi-monthly report focuses on the changing relations people have had with death during the COVID-19 pandemic	Beljaars D. & Shubin, S. (SU)	Brochure
14	March 2023	"I think we should have shown more empathy as a state" – A critical reflection of the COVID-19 response in Austria	It provides a reflection on pandemic management in Austria pointing out the negative consequences of the pandemic on vulnerable groups	Adler, V., Bertel D. & Bagheri, R. (SYNYO)	Brochure
15	May 2023	Mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic and lesson learnt for future crisis	Interviews about the impact of the pandemic on mental health of vulnerable groups (e.g. HCWs, ethnic minorities...)	Ajala, H., (MDI)	Video interviews
16	July 2023	COVID-19 Communication Practices, Lessons Learned, and Recommendations	The report outlines the lessons learned and recommendations relating to communication across the COVINFORM project's Work Packages	Anson S. & Mehdi Z. (TRI)	Brochure

17	September 2023	Migrant women during the pandemic: multiple and intertwined vulnerabilities	The report presents findings on the qualitative fieldwork implemented within the project and in particular on migrant women with low socioeconomic status (SES).	Ambrosetti, E. (SAPIENZA) & Sánchez-Vitores, I. (URJC)	Brochure
18	October 2023	How to build and how to lose trust. Lessons learned and resident perspectives on crisis communication.	This report aims to show a different side of the pandemic and highlight the experience of those who carried the disproportionate load of the pandemic consequences, namely women with low socioeconomic status (SES).	Adler, V., Götz, V. & Bagheri R., (SYNYO)	Brochure

The reports ten to twelve contain findings from the research conducted within WP3-WP7. Specifically, in the report “Socio-economic Impact of COVID-19”, published in July 2022, are summarized the findings about socio-economic consequences of COVID-19, reporting summary of desk research conducted within COVINFORM with a focus on vulnerable populations and impact on different system. The eleventh report, published in September 2022, entitled “Resilience in the Systems we live in: 10 European case studies”, presents a glimpse on how the empirical research is carried out and further information on how the case studies contribute to the 7 Objectives of the COVINFORM project as well as how each relate to Work Packages 4-7. The twelfth report, “A civil society organisation perspective on vulnerability: Lesson learned during COVID-19”, published in November 2022, is building on qualitative interviews conducted with CSO representatives who work directly with vulnerable groups, and is complemented by two rounds of desk research, focuses on lessons learned by civil society organisations (CSOs) about vulnerability during the COVID-19 pandemic: specifically, about how health, economic, social, and informational vulnerabilities emerged and evolved within EU municipalities. Those three reports and the following one targeted academic and practitioners.

The thirteenth report, “‘Closer to death’: thinking about dying in pandemic times”, published in January 2023, focuses on the changing relations people have had with death during the COVID-19 pandemic. It is based on a survey study on which the Swansea University partner collaborated with the Swansea Bay University Health Board, Neath Port Talbot Council for Voluntary Services, and Swansea Council for Voluntary Services.

The fourteenth report, published in March 2023 and titled “‘I think we should have shown more empathy as a state’ – A critical reflection of the COVID-19 response in Austria” provides a reflection on pandemic management in Austria pointing out the negative consequences of the pandemic on socially vulnerable groups.

The fifteenth report, published in May 2023 and entitled “Mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic and lesson learnt for future crisis” is published in video format. Partners from MDI interviewed HCWs based in the UK about the impact of the pandemic on mental health of vulnerable groups. Additionally, two partners of the project Hannah Robinson (UAntwerpen) and Diana Beljaars (SU) were interviewed about the same issue and in particular on the fieldwork with vulnerable groups that they performed within the activities of the COVINFORM project.

The eighteenth report, published in October 2023 entitled “How to build and how to lose trust. Lessons learned and resident perspectives on crisis communication” focuses on COVID-19 communication and trust with a focus on the perception of vulnerable groups. The aim is to illustrate the voices of vulnerable groups, in particular, of women of low socioeconomic background. The purpose of this report is to show a different side of the pandemic and highlight the experience of those who carried the disproportionate load of the pandemic consequences.

The remaining part of the deliverable contains all the reports published so far. In the last section of the deliverable, a balance of this first part of bi-monthly reports is drawn and the next steps for the remaining bi-monthly reports are outlined.

2 Bi-monthly report 9-18

2.1 Bi-monthly report 9: After two years of pandemic: COVINFORM partners talk about the experiences, challenges and lessons learned

After two years of pandemic | COVINFORM Bi-monthly report #9, May 2022

COVINFORM partners talk about the experiences, challenges and lessons learned. Andreea Furtuna from the Romanian Red Cross (SNCR) and Massimo Fantoni from the Catholic University of the Sacred Heart (UCSC) and Itamar Laist from the Magen David Adom in Israel (MDA) describe the challenges they had to face in the various phases of the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing also on lessons learned and best practices that have been developed in the crisis situation related to the pandemic.

The full interview is available [here](#)

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dynamics Research and Modelling

Socio-Economic Impacts of COVID-19

Bi-Monthly Report: 10

Authors

Dalila Antunes, Sara Miccoli & Elena Ambrosetti

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The COVINFORM project aims to investigate the socio-economic impact COVID has had different domains of populations and societies, namely governments, public health, specific communities, and communication.

Desk research has been conducted for each area to identify issues, problems and indicators useful for analysis. Specific case studies and empirical research are being carried out to study specific consequences on certain categories of populations pertaining to the four domains.

COVINFORM INDICATORS & PRIMARY DATA COLLECTION

Examples of vulnerable groups identified

- Healthcare Workers
- Migrant Workers
- Asylum Seekers
- Single/Lone parents
- Clinically Vulnerable
- Women Victim of Domestic Violence
- Homeless and Drug Dependent
- Gypsy & Traveller Community

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a variety of consequences on the various systems that constitute today's societies. Government systems have faced the development of measures to counter the virus. Health systems have experienced increased hospitalizations with major consequences on daily services. Family, community, and organization systems faced social, economic consequences of movement restrictions, in addition to those of the virus itself. The information system has been challenged by misinformation.

Some specific consequences of the pandemic have affected more than one sector of society simultaneously.

COVID-19 AND SOCIETY: THE IMPACT ON DIFFERENT SYSTEMS

GOOD PRACTICES

The pandemic, in addition to the numerous challenges, has also enabled the development of good practices.

Organization

- Ability to detect an upcoming crisis
- Well-functioning formal and informal networks: the importance of national-local communication
- Ability of organizing crisis responses and a clear chain of command
- Collaboration between different units

Technology

- Important public investments to improve network infrastructures, support distance learning and teleworking, improve forms of communication with citizens. Strong development of software and apps

Solidarity

- Towards native and immigrant populations in conditions of poverty and marginality or people with a drug addiction, sex workers, and homeless people
- Organisation and regulation of food banks, psychological support, information activities

Culture and respect for diversity

- Different solutions for different communities
- Cooperation with local leaders with high credibility (churches and mosques)
- Involving VIP also to combat the many fake-news on the social media and texting mobile apps
- Increase internet usage in those communities less familiar with technology

Cooperation

- Towards native and immigrant populations in conditions of poverty and marginality or people with a drug addiction, sex workers, and homeless people
- Organisation and regulation of food banks, psychological support, information activities

Door to door

- 'mobile clinics' travelling around the city
- 'vaccine vans' driven to particular sites where particular groups congregate

The COVINFORM project

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dynamics Research and Modelling

**Resilience in the
Systems we live in: 10
European case studies**

Bi-Monthly Report: 11

Authors

Patrick Love & Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto, FS

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RESILIENCE IN THE SYSTEMS WE LIVE IN: 10 EUROPEAN CASE STUDIES

This bi-monthly report presents an overview of the 10 COVINFORM's case studies which aim to identify vulnerability and protective factors of both vulnerable populations and the systems they are a part of, across different geographical settings: Portugal, Belgium, Spain, Italy, Austria, Germany, Sweden, Greece, Wales, and England. Each country selected a local site to understand how these factors enhance or mitigate COVID-19 impacts through different time points of the pandemic and contribute to provide recommendations for more effective policy making. Hence, this report presents a glimpse on how the empirical research is carried out and further information on how the case studies contribute to the 7 Objectives of the COVINFORM project and how each relates to Work Packages 4-7 may be found in Deliverables: D3.1; D3.4; and D3.5.

One of the aims of COVINFORM project is to identify and transfer best practices for boosting the well-being of vulnerable groups, and define guidelines to influence behaviour across different groups in a way that improves the well-being and mental health of the population, as well as the resilience of the systems in which vulnerable groups are a part of. Such broad, ambitious goals pose a challenge for the theoretical underpinnings of the project. The most pragmatic solution was to combine insights from the theory of complex adaptive systems with those of intersectionality theory.

Among other advantages, the complex systems approach recognises the need to work at multiple scales simultaneously if responses are to be effective. Concerning the pandemic, that means combining measures at the individual level such as wearing masks, through to large-scale international co-operation (to find vaccines for instance), along

with measures at national, regional or city scales, including lockdowns or shutting public services and facilities. A complexity approach also looks at how a given system both adapts to changes in other systems and helps shape these changes in a constant feedback process.

Intersectionality theory allows for an analysis that paints a more realistic picture than the rhetoric proclaiming “we’re all in this together”. It exposes how different groups are more at risk or have more influence over the course of events depending on gender, socioeconomic status, profession, level of education, age, migration status, culture, and so on.

By combining analyses of how systems interact with descriptions of how these interactions affect different members of society, COVINFORM case studies explore the diversity of COVID-19 impacts on so-called vulnerable groups across a wide range of countries and contexts. This allows policymakers and other actors to compare how populations and institutions interacted, and to draw lessons for improving resilience to future stresses and shocks. The studies focus on vulnerable populations, such as low socio-economic status groups and ethnic minorities, female frontline workers, and people with higher health-related risks. As part of COVINFORM, the case studies relate to four other work packages (WP): Government responses and impact assessment (WP4); Public health responses and impact assessment (WP5); Citizen and community responses and impact assessment (WP6); and Inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation (WP7).

Country Research partner	Case Study Name Main research question	Target Population
Portugal FS	<i>Resilience in long term care facilities of different socio-economic status: COVID-19 structural and psychosocial impacts on elderly residents in Évora, Portugal.</i> Which socio-ecological system characteristics of each type of long-term care facility produced more successful outcomes in mitigating Covid-19 impacts, and why?	Institutionalized elderly
Belgium UANTWERPEN	<i>Mental health impacts, needs and responses among migrant communities during the COVID-19 pandemic: a qualitative case study in Antwerp, Belgium.</i> How has the COVID-19 pandemic impacted migrant community members' mental health and wellbeing?	Migrant communities
Spain URJC & SAMUR	<i>The experience with social protection of vulnerable Latin American and Moroccan communities in Madrid.</i> What strategies, if any, did the local government put in place to tackle the COVID crisis on migrant communities?	
Germany SINUS Sweden UGOT	<i>Information seeking among ethnic minorities and socio-economic vulnerable groups in Sweden related to the implementation of protective measures and vaccination willingness.</i> What communication strategies and practices have local government, health authorities and stakeholders implemented to inform ethnic minorities about protective measures and vaccines?	
Wales SU	<i>The multiplicity of Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (BAME) migrant nurses' vulnerabilities in South Wales.</i> What structural issues (mobility, opportunity, access) affect the pandemic experiences of BAME overseas qualified nurses who work in South Wales hospitals?	Health care workers
Italy SAPIENZA & UCSC	<i>The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the well-being of health care workers.</i> What have been the consequences of the pandemic on the well-being of health workers' physical and mental status, and which socio-demographic groups of health care workers are at greatest risk of experiencing negative mental health consequences and/or family distress?	
Austria SYNYO	<i>Experiences of female frontline workers in supermarkets in Vienna, Austria.</i> How did female workers in SPAR supermarkets perceive the infection risk they were exposed to at their workplace?	Frontline workers
Greece KEMEA	<i>Policing in times of pandemic: impact on the role of law enforcement agencies (LEAs), governmental actors and policy makers and its effect on trust issues of vulnerable populations towards the former.</i> Personal perception of COVID-19: Impact on personal and professional environment.	
England MDI Ireland TRI	<i>Hard-to-reach communities in England.</i> What communication channels did hard-to-reach communities rely on during COVID-19?	Ethnic and religious minorities

The multilevel, multidisciplinary approach provided the flexibility needed to consider such a wide range of research topics, enabling the teams to adopt the most appropriate methodology for their particular investigation and compare findings to propose useful policy advice. For example, the Austrian case study of supermarket workers has to take account of numerous, well-documented internal rules and working practices plus government standards and regulations. The English study of the interplay between the mainstream COVID-19 narratives and alternative models of communication during the pandemic on the other hand, does not claim to be exhaustive or work with a representative sample of various religions and ethnicities, seeking rather input from “storytellers” whose experience can inform the broader narrative.

The case studies therefore cover a broad spectrum of issues and actors in the pandemic. Some of the research topics concentrate on the theory informing decisions and how this translated into effects on vulnerable groups. For example, the Italian governmental approaches to defining and addressing vulnerability had repercussions for health care workers and their families. Other studies describe the impacts and unintended consequences of response measures. The Belgian study for instance recognised early on an issue that has since come to the fore – the impact of restrictions imposed for physical public health reasons on mental health and well-being.

The baseline conditions of vulnerable groups strongly determined how the pandemic would affect them. The case study of migrants in Spain whose language skills and administrative status influenced how and if they could access resources and respond to the challenges the crisis posed. The authorities for their part have to be aware of the challenges involved in communicating with vulnerable groups in a crisis. The German and Swedish case studies look at this from both sides – local authority preparedness and communication activities; and the experience of local stakeholders.

The intersectionality approach proves important in studying groups characterised by multiple “identities” and possible sources of vulnerability.

Care home residents for example are often identified and treated according to a very limited set of criteria, perhaps only “old” and “needing care”. However, as the Portuguese case study illustrates, outcomes for what might seem like a homogenous group are varied and are determined by a range of social, psychological, cultural, institutional and other factors pertaining to both the residents themselves and those they interact with directly or indirectly.

The interactions between two systems are often mediated, so the Greek case study examines the impacts on an intermediary group, law enforcement agencies. In general, these agencies do not design policies, but they are often the most public face of policy implementation, and as such are vulnerable to the stress that can be generated by being caught between decisionmakers keen to see their COVID response measures adhered to, and members of the public who resent the restrictions.

To be complete, the case studies have to include important parameters that are not amenable to traditional data analysis. The study of nurses in Wales from Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic backgrounds therefore looks not only at their physical work and living spaces, but also at the imagined spaces of their homes in the Philippines and Caribbean, and how these influence coping strategies and resilience.

The COVID-19 pandemic started as a health shock, but the impacts quickly cascaded through numerous systems to generate economic, social and political crises. The case studies presented above shed light on the multitude of factors that shaped the way the crisis evolved at different levels. Some of the phenomena studied are local, but a number of common lessons, both positive and negative, can be drawn. This will enable policymakers and others to share good practices and avoid past mistakes, thereby contributing to higher resilience of institutions, individuals and communities in the future, particularly the most vulnerable.

ROADMAP

The COVINFORM project

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COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**A civil society
organisation perspective
on vulnerability: Lessons
learned during COVID-19**

Bi-Monthly Report: 12

Author

James Edwards, SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH

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INTRODUCTION

This report focuses on **lessons learned by civil society organisations (CSOs) about vulnerability** during the COVID-19 pandemic: specifically, about how health, economic, social, and informational vulnerabilities emerged and evolved within EU municipalities. It is based on qualitative interviews conducted with CSO representatives who work directly with vulnerable groups, supplemented by two rounds of desk research. We asked our CSO interviewees about...

- how they understood vulnerability;
- how the pandemic impacted the vulnerable groups they work with; and
- how their organisations helped address these groups' needs.

After framing CSO interviewees' insights on certain apparent 'properties' of vulnerability, we describe specific measures that CSOs took to help address the needs of vulnerable groups. Leveraging their local knowledge and community connections often enabled CSOs to reach groups with limited access to, or trust in, governmental institutions.

During the interviews, we kept an eye out for stories and situations that the interviewees themselves found surprising, thought-provoking, inspiring, or otherwise extraordinary. Borrowing the vocabulary of institutional analysis, we call these "**action situations**"ⁱ. This report is based on our findings in general, but takes special account of the action situations shared by our interviewees. We present these as moments from which CSOs and other stakeholders can learn when facing future crises.

ⁱ The institutional analysis and development framework and the social-ecological systems framework are two ways of thinking about the ways actors behave within complex systems. A critical concept in both frameworks is the action situation, in which "actors in positions make choices among available options in light of information about the likely actions of other participants and the benefits and costs of potential outcomes" (McGinnis & Ostrom 2014). Action situations are conditioned by the social and ecological systems in which they unfold, but also hold the potential to impact and change the parameters of these systems.

METHODOLOGY

This report is based on two phases of research performed in the COVINFORM project:

- **Desk research** on COVID-19 impacts, policies, and response measures in one municipality in each of the 15 project target countries. This included a review of primary sources (such as policy documents), secondary sources (such as scientific studies and grey literature), and, where available, quantitative data. A first round of desk research was conducted in Q2 2021, and a second round in Q3 2022.
- **Qualitative interviews** with N=5 representatives of civil society organisations (CSOs) or resident-organised initiatives involved in COVID-19 responses in a smaller subset of 10 target countries. To maintain a local focus, a best effort was made to recruit interviewees working in the specific municipalities on which the desk research was conducted, though in some cases, interviewees worked in nearby regions. The original fieldwork period was Q1 2022.

The interviews were transcribed and analysed by the research partners who conducted them, and the findings per interview and per site were reported using a standardised template. A cross-country analysis was then conducted, guided by the COVINFORM vulnerability assessment model and relevant theoretical frameworksⁱⁱ.

15 target countries:

Austria (Vienna)
Belgium (Antwerp)
Germany (Mannheim)
Greece (Athens)
Italy (Rome)
Portugal (Lisbon)
Spain (Madrid)
Sweden (Gothenburg)
UK: England (Birmingham)
UK: Wales (Swanse)

Cyprus,
Ireland,
Israel,
Romania,
Switzerland

ⁱⁱ The analysis made particular use of MacQueen et al.'s research on emic perceptions of community within vulnerable groups (2001) and Ostrom's social-ecological systems framework (McGinnis & Ostrom 2014). The findings per country/municipality and cross-country analysis are available in COVINFORM deliverables D6.3, "Analysis: Community and citizen responses and impacts" and D6.4, "Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts".

WHAT DID CSOS LEARN ABOUT VULNERABILITY DURING THE PANDEMIC?

Throughout our interviews with CSO representatives, we focused on vulnerability. We asked our interviewees how they understood vulnerability, both in general and specifically during the COVID-19 pandemic. Nearly all interviewees worked directly with vulnerable people: sometimes a specific group (like refugees or victims of domestic violence), and sometimes a range of individuals and groups in need of various kinds of support. Nearly all interviewees also stated that the impacts of the pandemic were especially severe for people who were already vulnerable. This came as no surprise to them. However, the pandemic’s confluence of health, social, economic, and informational risks did teach them lessons about the ways in which different vulnerabilities overlap and exacerbate one another.

Multidimensionality and cascades

For many interviewees, the pandemic showed how vulnerability is nearly always multidimensional. Individuals and populations that are vulnerable to risks in one domain – such as health or economics – are often vulnerable to risks in other domains as well (Assa & Meddeb 2021). Moreover, as illustrated in Figure 1, risks, vulnerabilities, and harmful outcomes in one domain can often cause or exacerbate vulnerabilities in other domains.

Figure 1. Vulnerability across domains

In socio-ecological systems research, this is called a **cascading effect**: we can envision risks, vulnerabilities, and harms cascading across the health, economic, social, and informational domains (Pescaroli & Alexander 2016). One threat highlighted by some interviewees is that cascading risks, vulnerabilities, and harmful outcomes might push individuals who were previously stable into a state of precarity, which they are unprepared to deal with, and from which it could be difficult to escape. A situation described by an Austrian interviewee exemplifies this threat:

- **Site:** Vienna, Austria
- **Interviewee:** a counsellor and social worker at the Vienna branch of a transnational aid organisation.
- **Other actors:** her client, in this case an interpreter with trouble finding work.
- **Action situation:** *“One example for me was a client who worked as an interpreter at conferences. Logically, she lost her income completely. And she only contacted me after half a year [...] because her savings had been used up. And these are just the kind of stories that are very difficult, because somehow people often don't want to admit that there is nothing that can save them, they simply have to change their lifestyle [...] The only thing she could do is give up her flat in the seventh district and register for a municipal flat. That is a much more difficult type of counselling [for us], also because it is often not accepted, simply because it is connected with disbelief”.*

This situation shows how the disproportionate impact of the pandemic and response measures on some sectors – such as live events – led to a sustained loss of income for people whose livelihoods had previously been secure. Within this particular situation, the actors’ choices were limited. However, the situation shows how in addition to addressing the needs of those who are already vulnerable, policymakers and first-line practitioners should watch out for emerging vulnerabilities during periods of crisis. Here, revisiting historical precedents could be helpful.

Networks

Interviewees made it clear that health, economic, social, and informational risks often affect not only vulnerable individuals, but others in their social circles as well. We could say that vulnerability is **networked**. Among the examples given of people impacted by vulnerabilities within their social circles were recipients of misinformation passed on through social media, families of people in care facilities, diasporic families, and parents of autistic children. Figure 2 illustrates how vulnerabilities can cascade through a network.

Figure 2. Vulnerability across domains

Considering networks is especially critical in risk communication. Interviewees who worked with migration-background target groups in particular emphasised how social networks (offline and online) were often the go-to source for information about the pandemic, rather than official channels. This sometimes facilitated the transmission of misinformation.

The most well-known example of this was the spread of vaccine myths among migration-background populations – cited, for instance, by interviewees in Germany, Sweden, etc. However, a situation described by an Austrian interviewee shows how other types of misinformation could spread as well:

- **Site:** Vienna, Austria
- **Interviewee:** a German teacher at a women's support organisation based in the second district of Vienna.
- **Other actors:** her clients, mostly Muslim women from north Africa and the middle and near east.
- **Action situation:** *“So, [our clients] were so torn, so afraid, that they kept to the measures insanely, very precisely. So, it was sometimes the case that we told them, hey, you have to take the children outside now and then, that's not possible [to keep them indoors all the time], they'll go crazy. And you can go out. But above all, they also had some relatives who actually died. So, in Afghanistan, in Syria, also in Morocco, sometimes the father or the brother died of Corona. They didn't handle it the way we do in Europe now. So, the women were also really afraid of this virus [...] actually, they all didn't know what was going on. But if you don't understand the newspaper and the news and can't follow it, then [...] on the one hand they were happy that they didn't have to go out, and on the other hand they really missed the German course. Because that's the only thing for many of them, apart from going shopping. They are always somehow with children or husbands, um, that's often why they like to come. It's a reason to go out and meet someone else, somehow. So, they were quite happy when we started again with the face-to-face classes.”*

This situation demonstrates how during crises that lead to social isolation, some target groups may have limited access to credible information about current conditions or regulations (e.g., via official information channels or the mainstream media). In this particular situation, extrapolating from news on conditions in their countries of origin led migrant-background women to constrain their own opportunities for meaningful social contact. Trusted CSOs can serve as intermediaries capable of providing timely information about conditions and encouraging its dissemination along their clients' social networks, thus supporting individual decisions that appropriately balance health risks against social and other risks.

Predictable and unpredictable outcomes

As mentioned above, nearly all of our interviewees stated that the pandemic's impact on those who were already vulnerable was especially severe. For most of them, this came as no surprise. Indeed, anticipating such impacts helped interviewees in Italy and Greece to partially mitigate certain risks in advance:

- **Site:** Rome, Italy
- **Interviewee:** a legal consultant for refugees and other migrants in Rome.
- **Other actors:** first-line practitioners in accommodations for refugees and other migrants.
- **Action situation:** *“The accommodation operators were very good. I must say they were very good. There were people who were reticent [to follow guidelines] – they really were not opposed, [but] they had difficulty understanding [...] But the operators were really good at this [...] They mobilized immediately. They tried to provide computers where they could, where they could to allow them to continue online classes when they were going to school, or when they were taking a course. Clearly, the very first wave was a little bit [about] figuring out how to organize, [but] they were really good I must say.”*

- **Site:** Athens, Greece
- **Interviewee:** a manager in a CSO that manages a network of accommodations for at-risk people, including the elderly, the houseless/homeless, and refugees.
- **Actors:** first-line practitioners and doctors in elderly care facilities; elderly residents; families of residents.
- **Action situation:** *“We implemented a quarantine before we were instructed by the municipality. We have a very good partner who is a doctor. Since early February [2020], he kept saying that the situation is not good and will get even worse. We began instructing visitors to wear gloves, and noticed that visitors did not abide by our recommendations, and we couldn't have an employee to frequently conducts checks. After a discussion with our doctor, we decided to implement a facility lockdown the very same day [...] the nationwide quarantine and measures in CSOs were implemented ten days after. It saved us, particularly our elder care facilities. If people respect these measures they can be lifesaving and effective. These observations are based on my two-year experience, as our CSO did not have a single casualty during this time period. Nevertheless, it was very emotionally draining, particularly for elderly citizens who had Alzheimer's disease who could not understand why their family would not visit them, and their families, as well as our employees, who [...]were afraid of getting infected and infecting our elderly patients.”*

Both the Italian and Greek situations show how to an extent, the multidimensional impacts of crises on vulnerable groups can be anticipated. Preparedness and quick adaptation from below are key competences that must be developed well in advance of a crisis itself.

However, the pandemic also led to numerous situations that defied our interviewees' predictions. For instance, interviewees in Belgium and Greece described how predicted risks and vulnerabilities did not always emerge, or at least not when expected.

- **Site:** Athens, Greece
- **Interviewee:** a decision-maker at a metropolitan religious CSO engaged in providing diverse social services, as well as supporting other CSOs.
- **Actors:** first-line practitioners in shelters; houseless/homeless residents.
- **Action situation:** *“There are many profiles of homelessness, drug and alcohol addicts, citizens that have make an earning out of begging [...] as well as mentally ill citizens, Roma homeless citizens, refugees and migrants, particularly during period of time that are characterized as high inflow eras [...] It may seem strange to you, as it did seem strange to me too, however, first of all, the infection rates among these people were very low. Why? Because they don't live with other people, and their epidemiological burden was the lowest in comparison to other groups. During lockdowns, there was a health-related issue due to the [lockdown] directives from the European Union and the government. There was an immediate need to shelter these people, which was very challenging, but we managed to do it in pre-existing facilities and new facilities that we created.”*

- **Site:** Antwerp, Belgium
- **Interviewee:** the coordinator at a CSO providing outpatient services for people with substance dependency issues.
- **Actors:** first-line practitioners at the CSO; clients with substance dependency issues.
- **Action situation:** *“We all expected that within our target group, the COVID-19 crisis would run rampant. We had actually expected this, because these people find it very difficult to stick to agreements, they follow very few hygiene rules, they hold on to each other very tightly in their peer group [...] We expected the contagion to spread very quickly, but that did not actually happen. Even though they are in unhealthy living conditions, there is a lot of infection risk in their behaviour, there have been few infections [...] And that's also why raising awareness has been so difficult. Because people said, 'well, you're exaggerating' or 'I'm not getting ill' or 'very little is actually happening'. We have had some serious cases and there, we have also had one person die in hospital. So it's not that nothing happened at all, but we had expected much, much more [...] There was also an attitude of: 'I've been through so much already in my life, I'll survive this one too for sure, it can just come and go, I've already had a lot of misery or problems – one more or less doesn't really matter.”*

In both situations, the interviewees described how infection rates and/or the risk of a serious progression remained lower than they predicted among their target groups. While good in and of itself, this made risk communication even more difficult than expected. Most people need to sense the immediacy and direct relevance of a crisis in order to be motivated to change their behaviour. In cases where people do not see a direct threat, or if they have more pressing issues to worry about, achieving behavioural change becomes challenging.

WHAT HELPED CSOS ADDRESS THE NEEDS OF VULNERABLE GROUPS?

Our interviewees discussed a range of ways in which lessons learned in the crucible of the pandemic helped them address their target groups' needs. Here, CSOs' ability to act on a **community level** often proved critical.

In the broadest sense, “communities” are simply groups of people that have something in common. A community can be geographical (i.e., a town), non-geographical (i.e., a professional community), or both (i.e., a community of co-nationals who have migrated to a certain city). In their research with members of different vulnerable groups, MacQueen et al. (2001) found that five factors are often perceived as especially important “elements of community”:

These elements of community play a role in experiences of vulnerability, as well as approaches to risk. For example, COVID-19 impacts varied by **location**; outcomes varied between groups with different **shared attributes**; and **joint actions** between CSOs, authorities, and ordinary residents were a critical part of many local response measures.

Our research shows that successful CSO responses to COVID-19 often consciously leveraged these elements of community.

Maintaining a local presence

To reach certain groups and meet their needs, it is critical to maintain a street-level presence in the places where they live and work. In the early days of the pandemic, when governmental services were closed or restricted, CSOs worked to keep their doors open. For instance, interviewees in Austria, Belgium, and Germany all indicated that their organisations made significant efforts to keep as many face-to-face services as possible running, and expressed pride in having done so. Later in the pandemic, CSOs helped ensure access to mobile services like vaccine vans. Beyond enabling unbroken access to services, a street-level presence helped CSOs to take the pulse in their neighbourhoods and design interventions tailored to site-specific problems. A Welsh interviewee gave an example:

- **Site:** Swansea, Wales
- **Interviewee:** a community engagement officer in the Swansea and Neath Port Talbot area, working directly with Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic (BAME) communities.
- **Other actors:** local businesses; local refugees and other migrants; Neath Port Talbot municipal authorities.
- **Action situation:** *“There were some issues identified, where certain sections of the community, they were not following the regulations and the rules, you know, having a face mask when they're going to the shop [...] keeping two meters distance, etc., in some of the local shops. There were issues we identified – like language was one of the key issues – because people [shopkeepers and other customers] didn't realize there were migrants who came recently there, you know, refugees and asylum-seekers who came in recently [...] from different countries, different places – they were used to different rules and regulation. In Wales, we have very specific rules and regulation. Like, in England, they are following completely different rules and regulation. So, what we have done, then, is arrange our environmental health team within the [Neath Port Talbot] Council, to provide a session to all the kinds of key businesses, for them to be aware of their responsibilities. And you know, if they don't follow the rules and regulations, then what would be the implications, including shutting the shop, etc.”*

In this case, customers' breaches of COVID-19 regulations could have put businesses at risk of having to pay a fine, or even close down. A secondary risk is that businesses or other customers may have reacted confrontationally to people violating the regulations. In this case, the interviewee's local knowledge enabled him to assess this potentially sensitive situation and do targeted awareness-raising work to mitigate these overlapping risks.

Sharing trust and solidarity

CSO interviewees emphasised the importance of gaining target groups' trust. This requires consistent demonstrations of solidarity and mutual understanding. Trusted CSOs are particularly critical intermediaries for groups marginalised by mainstream social institutions. For example, a Welsh interviewee testified to how the trust she had earned within the Gypsy, Roma, and Traveller (GRT) community allowed her to coordinate a successful vaccination action:

- **Site:** Swansea, Wales
- **Interviewee:** an engagement officer working with Gypsy, Roma, and Traveller (GRT) communities near Swansea, Wales.
- **Other actors:** GRT communities; the National Health Service.
- **Action situation:** *“We were quite lucky, but [COVID] didn't seem to spread very much at all in the sites. And we had a couple of people who had it, that really weren't affected that much. And then it came to a gentleman who passed away on the site through COVID. We had a couple that had been taken into hospital. And then we had the gentleman who passed away, and I think that was when the alarm bells really rang. Because we have quite a few community members who were of similar age, if not older, but with very similar health conditions [...] And then I had gypsies and travellers ring me up that day; ‘I need my vaccine, where can I get a vaccine?’ [...] So we rang up the NHS – like, our COVID line, spoke to a lady and within about 10 minutes, I had another lady ring me back, I called back and we were like ‘Wait, what are we going to do?’ And I was like; what she said ‘How many people do you think would want to be vaccinated?’ I said ‘at the moment, I said, I've got about 15 people that have spoken to me they want their vaccinations. Should we do a bespoke clinic for the Pembrokeshire Gypsy community?’ And within a week, we had 100 people wanting to do a vaccination. We had a van come down from the Llanelli area and set up in an airfield near us, with nurses and vaccines. I think that day we vaccinated 90-odd community members”*

Here, the death of a community member opened up a window of opportunity for vaccination. The first touchpoint for many GRT community members who suddenly wanted to be vaccinated was not the National Health Service (NHS) itself, but rather the interviewee, who had earned respect in the community through sustained solidarity (e.g., giving out her mobile number, being available for ad-hoc consultation on nearly any topic, etc.). Equally important, however, was the quick response the interviewee received from the NHS. Without either of these factors, it is possible that this window of opportunity would have been missed.

Leveraging social networks

Many interviewees indicated that their target groups relied strongly on their own social networks for information, as well as for material and social support. Especially in the case of marginalised groups, these networks may partially substitute for mainstream information sources and formal support institutions. Trusted CSOs or community members can sometimes leverage these networks when public authorities cannot. In some cases, as in Gothenburg, Sweden, local authorities took advantage of this capacity through formal or semi-formal “ambassador” or “guide” programs:

- **Site:** Gothenburg, Sweden
- **Interviewee:** a bilingual and bicultural “vaccine guide” employed by the City of Gothenburg.
- **Other actors:** other “vaccine guides”; their social circles.
- **Action situation:** *“In our network, for example, my friends, my contacts, and their contacts – yes, we had a huge network, and we worked on this network. And I believe we [vaccine guides], using this network, had a greater influence compared with my official work. The network was the most important factor [...] It is important that you receive information in your own language, and we are important to build trust, because I don’t just come and say ‘I am a health guide/cultural guide’. People have known me for 15 years and trust me, and then you listen to the information. Around 400-500 families in the local community know us and every time there is a new family moving in, they will ask for our help.”*

Here, the interviewee acted not only as a multiplier, but also as an access point through which accurate information could enter, and disseminate through, social networks that are rather isolated from official communications channels. Figure 3 illustrates this.

Figure 3. Using social networks to amplify risk communication

It is critical to note that such networks are not based on shared ethnicity alone, but rather on local presence and trust. Maintaining access to these networks would require the government to invest in a sustainable relationship with the “vaccine guides”. Unfortunately, interviewees indicated that this was not currently done: contracts were often temporary, and benefits were not commensurate with the value of the work done.

Demonstrating respect for differences

Nearly all of our interviewees characterised the areas in which they work as highly diverse. Many indicated that working with particular vulnerable groups required understanding sense-making and decision-making processes that differed from “the mainstream”. Some even described situations in which the needs of one vulnerable group collided with the needs of another: i.e., when interventions designed to help one group could be seen as threatening another. An interviewee in Germany described how working to understand and respect two very different groups allowed her to mediate between them:

- **Site:** Mannheim, Germany
- **Interviewee:** a decision-maker in a well-established local Christian church.
- **Other actors:** refugee and other migrant residents; elderly non-migration-background residents.
- **Action situation:** *“When I came here, there were several communal accommodations for refugees in the neighbourhood of the church. There were small apartments where families lived in three rooms with five or seven children, and these children just wandered around the church. And whenever I went out the front door, at some point I constantly had a child on my hand asking, where are you going, what are you doing, what are you doing now? And at the same time, the old people in the church were like, these kids are snotty and they're always accosting you, and I was like, you have to do something. The children were also afraid of the old people, and there was such a mutual fear. And I thought, you have to find encounters in which they can understand each other, first get to know each other, and then understand each other, and that's how this Generation and Children's Breakfast [a regular, free communal meal, to which elderly churchgoers and young migration-background residents were both proactively invited] came about. I very quickly brought in the students from the student community, and it was really incredibly interesting how quickly it succeeded, that the children then said, ah, this is Grandma Uschi and Grandpa Jürgen, and when they met someone on the street from the community, they said, may I carry your bag, and then didn't run off with it, and then they didn't run off with it to steal it, but really wanted to carry it, and the older people very quickly understood that these children had incredibly difficult stories behind them [...] community is not just a group of people coming together, but also a perception of who else belongs and who we want to include.”*

By creating a space in which different groups could come to better understand one another, the interviewee planted the seeds for mutual respect. In this case, she was able to transform intra-community diversity from a potential risk into a resource.

Coordinating joint action

The pandemic has demonstrated time and time again the importance of joint action between CSOs, governmental organisations, and ordinary people. This can take many forms, from coordinated cooperation under governmental umbrella programs to self-organisation by groups of residents. Several interviewees – for instance, in Spain and Greece – told how during the early phase of the pandemic, when public authorities and services were struggling to find their footing, CSOs took a leading role in initiating joint action to address critical needs:

- **Site:** Athens, Greece
- **Interviewee:** decision-maker at a CSO focused on children and youth.
- **Other actors:** other CSOs; municipal authorities.
- **Action situation:** *“The system of child protection in our country is understaffed and underfunded, and due to this fact, the national mechanism was not ready to address the social consequences of COVID-19 – which is why several agencies ceased their activities due to challenges [...] During the pandemic, we managed to establish cooperation with governmental and non-governmental organizations, such as municipalities, and have created a cooperative network for emergency responses that protect children and abused women. Since we lack a set protocol on how networks operate, and the modus operandi differ between different actors, sometimes conflicts can exist... nevertheless, in many cases the network does cooperate in a solid manner.”*

- **Site:** Madrid, Spain
- **Other actors:** director of a CSO providing numerous services to diverse vulnerable groups, with particular focus on young migrants.
- **Other actors:** other CSOs; eventually, public
- **Action situation:** *“This was the first time we have had a pandemic in the world – in this case in the western world – of this size and at a global level. The administration's systems were not accessible. Moreover, there was no public presence in [governmental service] centres, nor was there access by telephone – they worked internally, but not with citizens, it took many, many months until the public workers, the civil servants, could be accessed [...] We have never closed, never, never, not even in confinement, we were open because there were basic needs that we had to meet [...] I think it's important to see networking. Networking and articulated work are necessary. I think that in this aspect, in our area, we are always weaving a network. And we are always open to working with all entities, we have a principle. Every entity that lives and works within the framework of human rights is welcome [...] in December we exclusively asked for help from [another local CSO] to deliver bags of food. And previously, we also ran a campaign, in the middle of confinement, with friends that we have. So, with them we raised money, and also delivered many bags of food. Both here and in peoples' countries of origin. So [...] there are a lot of very generous people. What they do ask of you – and it's good – is that you be transparent.”*

The first of these anecdotes focuses on cooperation between CSOs and governmental organisations, while the second focuses on cooperation between multiple CSOs, as well as the participation of ordinary residents as volunteers and donors (including across borders). Both illustrate how responding effectively to a multidimensional crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic requires bridging between different sectors, stakeholder groups, and ways of workingⁱⁱⁱ. If such efforts at bridging are effective and sustained, they can incubate other success factors such as mutual trust, social ties, and respect for differences.

iii Folke et al. (2005) argue that “bridging organisations” play a critical role in the multilevel governance of natural resources, insofar as they support different actor groups in cultivating “social sources of resilience”: social capital, social learning, and social memory (p. 444). Based on our findings, we suggest that bridging organisations are equally critical in the multilevel governance of crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. For more on CSOs as bridging organisations, see COVINFORM deliverable D6.4, “Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts”.

CONCLUSIONS

This report offers a civil society organisation (CSO) perspective on how vulnerabilities and risks emerged and evolved during the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as how they can be addressed. It points out some general ‘properties’ of vulnerability: health, economic, social, and informational vulnerabilities tend to be multidimensional and historically situated; they tend to cascade across domains; they impact multiple people within social networks; and they can precipitate unpredictable outcomes. The report also draws out insights on how CSOs can help mitigate vulnerability on a community level by maintaining a local presence; fostering bonds of trust; taking advantage of social networks; demonstrating respect for differences; and coordinating actions that involve multiple stakeholder groups. A number of “action situations” collected from numerous sites illustrate the role of local, communally-embedded CSOs in fighting a crisis that ended up evolving into something much more than a public health emergency. Such CSOs can act as bridging organisations between governments and local communities, reaching vulnerable groups on the one hand and providing local knowledge to governmental stakeholders on the other.

What this report does not offer is an analysis of the power structures behind vulnerability. Doing so entails shifting from a multidimensional perspective on vulnerability to an intersectional perspective. The COVINFORM consortium gives an introduction to intersectionality in our fifth bi-monthly report, “Using an intersectional lens to understand the unequal impact of the COVID-19 pandemic” (Molenaar 2021). The project’s ongoing research with a range of vulnerable groups will help clarify the role of socioeconomic disparities and other power relationships in the articulation of COVID-19 impacts and responses. We hope that the outcomes will help CSOs and other actors to address not just the symptoms, but also the structural and political causes of multidimensional vulnerability.

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COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**‘Closer to death’:
thinking about dying in
pandemic times**

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Author

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INTRODUCTION

This bi-monthly report focuses on the changing relations people have had with death during the COVID-19 pandemic. It is based on a survey study on which the Swansea University partner collaborated with the Swansea Bay University Health Board, Neath Port Talbot Council for Voluntary Services, and Swansea Council for Voluntary Services. The full report can be accessed here: <https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/country-reports/>

"Death strikes in the now, and immediately drives its shock wave into the future and down the past of that life. Death strikes, reducing to nothing the instrument she had made of herself in the world of work, reducing to nothing her individual identity."

- Alphonso Lingis, *Dangerous Emotions* (2000), page 120

As of 30 December 2022, the number of people who have died with COVID-19 as contributing factor has reached 11,237 in Wales, with Swansea Council posting 909 deaths and Neath Port Talbot 627 (Duffy, 2023). With 55 COVID deaths in the community, the Sandfields area in Port Talbot is second on the list of worst hit communities in Wales. On 10 January 2023, since March 2020, the Office for National Statistics records 8,715 more deaths in Wales in comparison with the five-year, non-pandemic average. On a population of 3.1 million and over the course of almost 3 years, these mortality numbers have had several implications for how the pandemic was experienced and what lasting legacies it leaves for individuals.

Death has been a central theme in the experience of pandemic times for many people. Echoing Alphonso Lingis' opening quotation, the possibility of dying prompted increased anxiety and fear of possible personal demise and feelings of hopelessness and uncertainty.

Some facts about the 'Health and Wellbeing Service Engagement' Survey:

	<p>It consists of 50 multiple choice answers, slides and Likert scales, and open-ended questions</p>
	<p>The data collection took place online and in person</p>
	<p>It has 139 respondents for the majority of the questions and for a minority it has 173 respondents.</p>
	<p>The survey results are not statistically representative of the Swansea, Neath, and Port Talbot areas, nor of the populations.</p>
	<p>The questions touched on themes such as life changes, vulnerability, vaccination, health service accessibility, and social relations.</p>
	<p>The largest survey demographic consists of women between the age of 25 and 54 who live in Swansea</p>
	<p>Ethnic background of respondents: 85% belong to ethnic minorities in Wales, this includes mixed and multiple ethnicities, with the largest groups consisting of Bangladeshi, Pakistani, Indian, Black African and Caribbean people, and 15% White people.</p>

Reflecting the experience of the survey respondents, many people reported knowing several others in their social circles and communities who have passed away. Even for those who do not personally know people who have died after being infected with the virus, death has been on their mind in more intense forms due to widespread information in the media. Survey respondents remarked on the intensification of feelings of anxiety, fear, and depression in relation to the fear of death in broadly four themes.

4 THEMES

1. Nearness of death

As the survey suggests, the most common theme in shifting thoughts around death during the pandemic is the realisation that death is not always preceded by long and ‘complete’ life or a period of illness. Rather, respondents more strongly consider the possibility of death to happen “at any time” or even “now” and be “closer” than they previously thought. Appealing to their sense of safety and protection, death is perceived as being “near” or “closer to home”, which is perceived as “cruel” and “daunting”. Equally, according to the qualitative comments in the survey, death takes place “anyhow” and alluding to its inescapability, one “can’t avoid it”. In addition, in relation to ideas about living a fulfilled life, the COVID-19 pandemic made people particularly worried about dying “early”. Whilst death may not be early or late in experience, the anxiety that comes from realising that dying quickly will be rooted in more existential thoughts about the meaning of life and one’s place in the world.

2. Social thoughts about dying of COVID

Another set of new thoughts about death are about life after people have died and concerns about those who continue living. This alludes to how people can feel deeply responsible for others in their social circle. Indeed, many survey respondents point out how it worries them that their loved ones or family may struggle to cope without them if they come to pass away from COVID. Often it also involves taking on the grief and sense of loss for another person when they are struggling with the death of another person who they held dear. These thoughts then express in increased stress, fear and anxiety about the virus. A Muslim woman from a non-white non-listed ethnic group who is a student aged 18-24 from Port Talbot says that “It’s sad, I can’t sleep properly when I think about it”.

3. Randomness of victimisation

Another set of new thoughts about death are about life after people have died and concerns about those who continue living. This alludes to how people can feel deeply responsible for others in their social circle. Indeed, many survey respondents point out how it worries them that their loved ones or family may struggle to cope without them if they come to pass away from COVID. Often it also involves taking on the grief and sense of loss for another person when they are struggling with the death of another person who they held dear. These thoughts then express in increased stress, fear and anxiety about the virus. A Muslim woman from a non-white non-listed ethnic group who is a student aged 18-24 from Port Talbot says that “It’s sad, I can’t sleep properly when I think about it”.

4. Confirmation of presence

This reported type of feeling about death during the pandemic was mentioned most by respondents who have had death as regular and consistently present element in their lives before the pandemic. This would pertain mostly to people who have had suicidal thoughts or who possibly have had to work through a death-related personal trauma, such as the death or illness of a loved one or their own illness or disability existing before the pandemic. As other studies suggest, the virus may have become another reason for generalised anxiety and thinking about death (Pérez-Mengual et al. 2021), particularly as a way to have control over their death, which is also evident among our survey respondents. Strategies to cope with these pandemic pressures increased and intensified thoughts about death and its nearness and inevitability. According to the survey results, during the pandemic people seem to pray more and speak more with family and friends in relation to the fear of death. One respondent stated that

"I wrote a message for my kids, making my Dad smile because life is so short we not guaranteed today let alone tomorrow" (Muslim woman, aged 45-54).

Thinking about death expresses symptoms related to anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (Murphy et al. 2021), with respondents in our survey reporting prevalent feelings of sadness and paranoia, which tend to be accompanied by problems with sleep.

In conclusion, the COVID-19 pandemic has at least temporarily reconfigured ideas about death, which can alter what circumstances and risks are associated with dying, what kind of behaviours are perceived as dangerous, and what kind of response is viable. Perceptions of and attitudes towards death also change depending on the type and tone of messages in pandemic communication to which people are likely to respond. Healthcare organisations therefore ought to take note of such changes – even if perhaps minute – when communicating new policies, support services, and other requirements to the public.

THOUGHTS ABOUT FINALITY

Alphonso Lingis (quoted above) reminds us that in catastrophic times when we think about death, we have no choice but to think of all of life in all its overwhelming complexity. The pandemic makes us shed new light on how our lives are so entangled with others' and renew our pasts and futures.

Indeed, in the survey particularly pertinent seems to be the renewed realisation of the inevitability of death and the speed at which it can occur. Defying notions of old age, ill health, and disability as leading to imminent demise, bodies that are more vital (young, healthy, and abled) during the pandemic seen more within reach of death than ever before. Such concerns do not only affect a specific individual but may extend to the younger and fitter family members who had been considered relatively far removed from a possibility of an 'early' death.

As such, the survey outcomes echo Menzies and Menzies' (2020: np) recommendation that "treatment programmes in mental health may need to broaden their focus to directly target the dread of death" in the broadest sense and make this sensitivity an integral part of healthcare provision.

One way of staying with death in a productive manner can be with the recommendations in the Cambridge University 'A Good Death?' project. As Dr Laura Davies explains, the project aims "to help people to think and talk about human mortality in a reflective rather than a reactive way". She offers four suggestions: (1) acknowledge the suffering COVID-19 is causing, (2) normalise conversations about death within our personal relationships, (3) reflect on and deepen our own thoughts and feelings about death by actively exploring literature and the arts, and (4) ask questions.

Further Reading

‘A Good Death?’ project: https://www.cam.ac.uk/stories/BeyondThePandemic_agooddeath

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Pérez-Mengual, N., Aragonés-Barbera, I., Moret-Tatay, C., & Moliner-Albero, A. (2021). The Relationship of Fear of Death Between Neuroticism and Anxiety During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Frontiers In Psychiatry*, 12.

The COVINFORM project

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Contact

Consortium	SYNYO GmbH (SYNYO) , Austria Magen David Adom in Israel (MDA) , Israel Samur Proteccion Civil (SAMUR) , Spain Universita Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC) , Italy SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH (SINUS) , Germany Trilateral Research LTD (TRI UK) , UK Trilateral Research LTD (TRI IE) , Ireland Kentro Meleton Asfaleias – Center for Security Studies (KEMEA) , Greece Factor Social Consultoria em Psicossociologia e Ambiente LDA (FS) , Portugal Austrian Red Cross (AUTRC) , Austria Media Diversity Institute (MDI) , UK Societatea Națională de Cruce Rosie Din România – Romanian Red Cross (SNCRR) , Romania University of Antwerp (UANTWERPEN) , Belgium Sapienza University of Rome (SAPIENZA) , Italy University Rey Juan Carlos (URJC) , Spain Swansea University (SU) , UK Gotenborg University (UGOT) , Sweden
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COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**"I think we
should have shown
more empathy as a state"
- A critical reflection of the
COVID-19 response
in Austria**

Bi-Monthly Report: 14

Author

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Adler, V., Bertel D. & Bagheri, R. (2023). “I think we should have shown more empathy as a state” - A critical reflection of the COVID-19 response in Austria Bi-monthly report 14, March 2023. COVINFORM H2020 Project No. 101016247

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INTRODUCTION

Although COVID-19 started as a health crisis, it quickly became more than that, affecting all areas of life. By now, almost all restrictions were lifted, yet restrictions and – at times – their negative consequences – particularly on vulnerable groups – were part of our lives for the past three years. Thus, we want to use this point in the pandemic to reflect on Austria’s pandemic management. Based on our findings we argue that the initial public health responses and their primary focus on minimising COVID-19 transmission, and death (along with financial mitigation strategies) were necessary and good. However, three years have passed. Yet, official definitions of vulnerability and responses have not been updated; they are still focused rather narrowly on medically vulnerable people, and, to some extent, groups with an elevated risk of exposure to the virus. This report, based on the ongoing research realized within COVINFORM, clearly indicates that certain groups have fallen through the cracks in this framework, suffering ongoing harm. A focus on health outcomes ignores the lived experience of those outside of the norm of the white (male) middle-class nuclear family and those who are affected by structural inequality.

Vulnerability can be defined as “the conditions determined by physical, social, economic, and environmental factors or processes, which increase the susceptibility of [an individual or] a community to the impact of hazards” (UN/ISDR, Geneva 2004; cited in United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction 2005). In this report, we reflect on vulnerability and what is needed to create a crisis response that allows all groups to live their lives well — as much as this is possible in a crisis. To do so, we follow Atkinson’s et al. (2019) critique of common approaches to community wellbeing. Building on that critique, we contemplate how, in the face of the multiple crises affecting our lives, a concept of community wellbeing could be drawn upon to create crisis living conditions that do not privilege one sort of vulnerability over others. Specifically, we explore three dimensions defined by the authors: 1) inequality, 2) scale, and 3) temporality. Reconsidering COVID-19 responses along these dimensions pushes us to give more space to underlying inequalities; to shift from a narrow concept of (individual) health to a more communal approach to wellbeing.

METHODOLOGY

The first step of the research realised within COVINFORM, consisted of desk-based research, followed by a document review, to gain an understanding of the pandemic responses. The documents reviewed were collected between March 2020 and November 2022. We focused on the following dimensions of COVID-19 pandemic management: government, public health, community and civil society, as well as crisis communication. This analysis was followed by expert interviews with 1) government officials, policymakers, and public authorities, 2) public health practitioners and experts, and 3) representatives of civil society organisations (CSOs). Additionally, we conducted 12 interviews with women of low socio-economic backgrounds in the City of Vienna. All interviews analysed for this report were conducted between November 2021 and October 2022 in Vienna (Austria).

Table 1. Interviews conducted in Vienna, Austria for the empirical research of COVINFORM project

Stakeholders type	Number of interviews
interviews with government officials, policymakers, and public authorities	4
interviews with public health experts	4
interviews with CSO representatives	4
Interviews with low SES women	12

THE (PROBLEMATIC) FOCUS ON HEALTH VULNERABILITIES IN THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

In the documents we reviewed, the Austrian government, understand vulnerable groups as those who are at higher risk of suffering from severe symptoms and to whom the disease could potentially be life-threatening: these are people aged over 65 years as well as people with (chronic) pre-existing conditions of all ages(ref). The most important document in relation to this is the so called *COVID-19 Risikogruppen-Verordnung* (COVID-19 risk order)¹. The order itself was updated but never extended beyond health vulnerabilities. As a government representative point out, the focus was on medical indicators:

“We solved this through a legal perspective... that these under quotation marks vulnerable groups who are still active on the labour market... they were defined and they are allowed... more or less... to permanently work in home office. That means that there is a definition. There are medical indicators and there is the right for these people to stay in the labour market, but just from their homes.” (Government_1, Austria)

The other important document in relation to defining vulnerability in Austria is the document that outlined the prioritisation for the COVID-19 vaccination, established by the NIG (Nationales Impfgremium/National Vaccination Committee). This was the roadmap to Austria’s vaccination program².

“Finally, this was done by the “national” definition. More specifically through the NIG through the prioritisation they established in terms of vaccination. We know that vulnerability is the age of a person, particular medical constellations, this means risk factors and exposure. This is not a bad definition. So, if you think about it, you can even observe this.” (Government_2, Austria)

The document outlines, on the one hand, health risks like chronic disease or pre-existing conditions and, on the other hand, exposure to the virus (in a work setting). The focus on exposure adds a different layer to the definition of vulnerability: it moves beyond a focus on health status towards the likelihood of getting infected due to exposure during work. Nonetheless, the focus on health outcomes remained. However, focusing on exposure meant that teachers or health care staff were recommended for early vaccination. In Austria, these are often professions with lower income and a high percentage of women in the workforce. As such, the focus shifted, to some extent, to groups who felt the negative social impact of COVID-19 more strongly.

¹ https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2020_II_203/BGBLA_2020_II_203.pdf#sig

² <https://www.aekkt.at/documents/e031f3c0-4066-11eb-a558-5254009ad2fe/Empfehlung%20des%20Nationalen%20Impfgremiums%20zur%20Priorisierung%20von%20COVID-19-Impfungendocx.pdf>

AN ALTERNATIVE PERSPECTIVE ON VULNERABILITY DURING COVID-19

Spatial and social inequalities

Interviews with stakeholders in Austria revealed a wider range of understandings of vulnerability and inequality than were present in official definitions. While some stakeholders – particularly in higher levels of government – hewed close to official definitions, other stakeholders – particularly in local government and CSOs – expressed concepts of vulnerability that went beyond official definitions. They mentioned multiple other harms and other forms of vulnerability imposed by the pandemic, such as the double care burden for women, the loss of jobs in precarious settings, or the psychosocial pressure of isolation, especially for the very old and young.

Table 2. Vulnerable groups that came up most often in the interviews with stakeholders

Main group	Subgroup(s)
Refugees and other migrants	
Women and children in high-risk situations	Those subject to familial/partner violence
	Sex workers
People working in precarious or otherwise unfavourable conditions	Meat workers
	Farm workers
	Short-contract workers
People living in precarious or otherwise unfavourable conditions	The houseless/homeless
	People living in crowded flats/buildings
	People living month-to-month
The socially excluded	Addicts
	The mentally ill
	Runaway youth
Economically precarious families and individuals in general	
People with information/communication vulnerabilities	Refugees and other migrants with no or little knowledge of the local language
	Those with learning disabilities or cognitive challenges
	Those with little formal education

Here, vulnerability is directly linked to pre-existing structural inequalities. The way these vulnerabilities were framed in the interviews highlights that they are often perceived through the lens of ‘a lack of capability’ of groups and individuals to protect themselves from the virus and other negative consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic. One of the reasons we heard most where so-called communication vulnerability, i.e., communication barriers or challenges that people experience while living through a pandemic. There are multiple reasons why groups or individuals lack crucial information about potential risk and strategies to mitigate these risks.

“For me, these (vulnerable groups) are people who are hard to reach through the media because they do not consume them for various reasons...when they are homeless or something similar...so that they do not participate in social life or do not want to or it is just not really possible for them. And, the third group would be people that... because of ... different barriers for example language barriers...that are not that easy to reach as let’s say the average citizen.” (Government_3, Austria)

CSO representatives often expressed nuanced understandings of the ways in which COVID-19 multiplied spatial and social inequalities that harm not only physical health, but wellbeing more broadly understood:

“[...] our classical clients they are not so much affected by income loss due to COVID-19 because they are basically always in a state of financial crisis. The things you recognise in relation to vulnerability is then that.. particularly in the beginning....when everybody was in sheer panic...because nobody knew how this virus really works ...and really everybody stayed at home...some issues really became visible. Many single mothers that.. normally have dinner with their parents three or four times a week with their children...they stopped doing this because the parents are 70, 75 and they were too scared to infect their parents. And, then you realise that even though the social system in Vienna is not bad... but that people still need informal support from family and their community to get by [...].” (CSO_2, Austria)

This is underlined by the experiences of a young and married mother of three children who is of low socio-economic and migrant background, living in Vienna. Her family’s housing situation could be described as living in overcrowded condition which can lead to bad health and mental health outcomes, particularly during a pandemic³. Further, in Austria it is a structural problem that migrants, particularly those of lower educational background, have less living space available than Austrian families⁴. As such, marginalised groups do not only suffer from less available resources but potentially also, as a consequence of their lack of resources, from worst health and mental health outcomes.

¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK535289/#:~:text=Household%20crowding%20is%20a%20condition,the%20dwelling%20and%20the%20household>.

² Berger, Tania, Czerny, Margarete, Faustmann, Anna, Perl, Christian (2014) Sozialraumanalyse: Konzepte und Empfehlungen zur Umsetzung von Integration in Niederösterreich. Erstellt vom Department für Migration und Globalisierung der Donau- Universität Krems im Auftrag des Amtes der Niederösterreichischen Landesregierung. Schriftenreihe Migration und Globalisierung, Krems (Edition Donau-Universität Krems)

“So, for now we have to stay in this apartment, in a 51m² apartment, we are five people. Let's see what will happen in the future years. And the living environment, my living environment, the environment outside where I go, overall, it's for me, it weakened my psyche a lot because it was very hard for me. Always with these children, three children. Then the language barrier with their language. I understand a lot but not so well. And Corona, as you say, came on top of that. Don't do this, don't do that, don't go there, do that. It made life very difficult and the environment. It made the situation difficult overall for us.” (Resident_3, Austria)

Multiple settings and scales

People “belong” to multiple communities that are associated with different scales and settings (Atkinson et al. 2019, p.1911). Understanding both vulnerability and community wellbeing thus requires examining interactions on multiple scales, in different settings, among multiple population groups and institutions. The interviews brought three types of scalar aspects to light.

First, interviewees often discussed the tensions inherent in Austria's federal governmental and public health system. At the beginning of the pandemic, the crisis response was centralised under the responsibility of the federal government, which was welcomed by the state provinces. This changed over the duration of the pandemic, with state and local authorities increasingly adapting federal guidelines to better suit the specific challenges they faced. Our interviewees often observed challenges and conflicts in this process, as can exemplified by the following quote.

“All in all, the crisis came rather suddenly and unexpectedly for most people, especially the rapidity of the development in Austria at the beginning of March 2020 with the uncertain prognosis of how it would continue. So, in my impression, everyone was very happy that there were corresponding guidelines and legal measures at the national level. And in the end, the federal provinces, but also the social partners, the operational organisations connoted this rather positively, so to speak, that there is now strong leadership, so to speak, that there are clear instructions, and that it was also clear for the population, so to speak, how they have to behave. Later on, however, things developed differently, didn't they? On the one hand, this leadership is no longer so clear, there have been many political disputes. Suddenly, in the last few months, there have been many developments where the federal government, the national level, has given up this control sovereignty and transferred it to the Länder (federal states) in the sense of federalism, which have then acted according to their own discretion, which has led to differences between the Länder, and that there has been more public debate about this and that the systems are no longer completely harmonised. Now, this lockdown, for example, is no longer at the instigation of the federal government, but at the instigation of the provincial governors and the Minister of Health.” (Government_2, Austria)

A related second aspect identified by interviewees was poor communication between actors in multi-level governance systems. For instance, interviewees often had difficulty communicating and coordinating with authorities. Interviewees also reported a lack of effective feedback mechanisms between authorities, residents, and intermediary CSOs. A representative of an CSO described the need to improve communication structures as follows:

“So, my contribution for the future will be that we as an organisation better connect the actors among each other. um [long pause] The experiences I had at the beginning, when we were in the Ministry of Health, were that we knew each other among the ministries, i.e. within the ministries, but cooperation across the ministry’s borders was very, very limited and sometimes it was not clear who was the contact person at eye level in the other ministry.”
(Government_1, Austria)

Third, we found that spatially remote events have distinct impacts on wellbeing on a local level. One example is the war against Ukraine, which representatives of CSOs indicated had put a strain on their organisations and communities. The following quote by a young Russian student living in Vienna illustrates how multiple scales impact on her life. The young woman moved to Vienna shortly before the COVID-19 pandemic hit and found herself isolated, particularly from locals, as she had little time to meet new people. In the quote, she is talking about the Russian war on Ukraine and how this ongoing event has influenced her social contacts in Vienna after already being isolated from locals for the first two years of the pandemic. She was looking forward to finally meet new people once the pandemic situation eased a bit. Then the war started, and she felt the need to connect with other Russians and Ukrainians who would understand how she feels. However, this left her isolated from her peers in Vienna.

“And the same thing going on right now, which is not connected to COVID but to the war situation, like second wave, when I felt like, okay it was started to go like into two directions of connections and more integration here, as now it’s open again but then the war starts and again it goes back to much more connection to people who actually understand this problem of being within these parameters.” (Resident_1, Austria)

Temporal choices and legacies

Wellbeing is constituted by multiple temporalities, which involve “the intimate flow of life-courses, intergenerational relations, processes of stability and sustainability, the longer trajectories of history, change and cultural heritage and the relationship between them” (Atkinson et al. 2019, p.1909). Looking at vulnerability, we see a parallel structure. Therefore, we need to consider temporality in the COVID-19 crisis response in a twofold way: first, we need to understand and take into account that social inequalities are historically embedded. Second, COVID-19 is an ongoing crisis that has spread over the course of more than three years. As such, the temporality of the crisis itself needs to be considered as the effects on society and people have changed with time. Yet, we can observe a lack of attention to temporality on several levels. Interviewed stakeholders often talked about ‘secondary effects’ of the measures. These ‘secondary effects’ are the unintended consequences of the pandemic management e.g., lockdown and include loneliness, social isolation, and decreases in mental health. Some stakeholders even describe them as more devastating than the disease itself, in particular loneliness. With every lockdown people suffered more and more under loneliness and isolation and their negative effects intensified as the pandemic continued.

“[...] the social exclusion of older people...this was already a topic prior to the pandemic but now it is an even more pressing issue. And by now we all know that mental health...not only for risk groups or vulnerable groups...that mental health is an important topic. If somebody is mentally well then this also positively impacts their immune system [...] so it is hard to create balance...between how strict can the measures be to protect people and is this still an ethical approach?” (Government_4, Austria)

While at the beginning of the pandemic it was a reasonable goal to protect at-risk groups from severe health consequences and, in the worst case, death by the disease by implementing measures such as lockdowns and physical distancing, with the duration of the pandemic, the ‘secondary effects’ of such measures became increasingly problematic. Despite this, the governments did not seem to consider the wide-ranging effects of the measures and did not adapt responses over the duration of the pandemic. By looking at temporality, we can observe that “inequalities are reproduced both structurally and affectively” (Atkinson et al. 2019, p.1916).

This leads us to another aspect of temporality and a second example: children and youth. During the pandemic, children and youth became a vulnerable group. This shows how vulnerability is relational and changes over time. At the beginning of the pandemic, this group was not thought of as vulnerable due to their minimal risk of serious illness. However, children and youth were increasingly seen as vulnerable as the lockdowns and isolation impacted their social and personal development. They were not allowed to go to school, which not only impacted their learning, but also minimised their social interactions during a crucial time of development. Once the vaccines were widely available for adults but not yet for children and youth, they also were categorised as medically vulnerable as they had less protection than most of the society.

“To be honest.. children, that is what I keep on thinking and youth. I have a 15-year-old daughter. She actually took the whole thing pretty well but in her class and school there were a few who really struggled...they really suffered.” (CSO_1, Austria).

This is also reflected by a woman of low socio-economic and migrant background we interviewed. She is a young single mother of three children. In this quote, she talks about the struggles of her young daughter who had difficulties coping with lockdown:

“And somehow there wasn't much room, you can't say that. But with children and they were just not allowed out, then that is. You're not allowed to play football. They liked to go to the big park and you're not allowed. [...]. For my daughter it was a bit difficult. She cried and I said it's all closed. And kindergarten is also closed. Show me, show me and we went to the kindergarten. The door was closed. I said look a few times and said it's closed, you're not allowed in and there somehow.” (Resident_12, Austria)

CONCLUSION

Our analysis showed that the Austrian pandemic management had a strong focus on health vulnerability and barely acknowledged other forms of social vulnerability. This is problematic as it has been proven by now that COVID-19 deepened pre-existing inequalities⁵. More so, after three years of living through a pandemic, we have seen that COVID-19 pandemic is more than just a health crisis: it affects all areas of life. Listening to the experiences of those directly involved in the pandemic management highlights that a shift from a health-based approach to a wellbeing approach would be more appropriate given the longevity of the crisis. When asking questions about inequality, scale and temporality, we can see how a.) COVID-19 impacts differently on various groups of people, b.) people are affected by multiple spheres reaching from the local to the national to the transnational one, c.) that risk and vulnerability are changing over time. These aspects create new pressure points for vulnerable populations which cannot fully be understood when focusing solely on health outcomes.

⁵ https://reliefweb.int/report/world/policy-brief-impact-covid-19-women?qclid=CjwKCAjwolqhBhAGEiwArXT7K8etj0MYes7MIV7z-q6osGCCpBf-rdHww1C9k-CwalGn1fIbenxkLvxoCKFQQAvD_BwE

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2.7 Bi-monthly report 15: Mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic and lesson learnt for future crisis

Bi-Monthly Report: 15 – ‘Mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic and lessons learnt for future crisis’

Partners from MDI interviewed HCWs based in the UK about the impact of the pandemic on mental health of vulnerable groups. Additionally two partners of the project Hannah Robinson (UAntwerpen) and Diana Beljaars (SU) were interviewed about the same issue and in particular on the fieldwork with vulnerable groups that they performed within the activities of the COVINFORM project.

The full interview is available [here](#)

COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**COVID-19
Communication
Practices, Lessons
Learned, and
Recommendations**

Bi-Monthly Report: 16

Authors

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INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the key role that communication plays throughout a crisis. Prior to the development and rollout of vaccines, government responses focused on communication policies and communicating protective measures the public should adopt, such as lockdown and “social distancing” (Fakhruddin, Blanchard and Ragupathy, 2020). Communication also supported the rollout of vaccines (Quinn et al., 2023).

While communication has a key role, it is also “one of the key factors that can either increase or decrease people’s vulnerability to disasters” (Hansson et al., 2020, p.1). The need to consider vulnerability when communicating in a crisis is highlighted by the whitepaper “Inclusive Communication in Times of Crisis” developed

by the COVINFORM and PROACTIVE projects. The whitepaper outlines how the pandemic has reinforced the differential impacts that a crisis has on different groups and how there is a need to engage with vulnerable groups to understand their information needs, concerns and barriers that may prevent them from following protective measures. This understanding should inform the design of communication.

Communication has therefore been a cross-cutting topic in the COVINFORM project. This bi-monthly report outlines the lessons learned and recommendations relating to communication across the COVINFORM project’s Work Packages (WPs). Particular attention will be paid to WPs 2-8, which focus on:

- The development of a risk assessment model to evaluate the response and impact at different geographical levels (WP2),
- Case study design and evaluation (WP3),
- Government responses and impact assessment (WP4),
- Public health responses and impact assessment (WP5),
- Citizen and community responses and impact assessment (WP6), and
- Inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation (WP7),
- The development of solutions, guidelines, and recommendations (WP8).

WP2: THE COVINFORM RISK ASSESSMENT MODEL

The COVINFORM project is creating an interactive risk assessment dashboard that will provide insights on different types of COVID-19 vulnerability (i.e., physical, social, economic and information) and the related impacts. The insights provided by the dashboard, that is being developed as part of WP2, can inform the design of risk and crisis communication. The dashboard will be made readily available at the end of October 2023.

The risk assessment dashboard is based on extensive and complementary quantitative and qualitative data collection practices. This includes a risk model that is based on quantitative data collected at a national level that covers; the threat (risk) of COVID-19; vulnerabilities; the consequences (impacts) of COVID-19; and resilience. The vulnerability data is further segmented to cover four categories of vulnerability:

- **Physical** (e.g., pre-existing health conditions)
- **Social** (e.g., education level, rural vs urban, gender, migrant population)
- **Economic** (e.g., GDP, % living in poverty, income inequality, unemployment rates)
- **Information** (e.g., literacy, digital access, digital skills)

The quantitative data available at the national level provides some high-level insights on vulnerability in a country that can be further explored. For instance, the data for information vulnerability may highlight low levels of digital access and the need to use traditional (e.g., print) communication channels to reach different groups. However, relying solely on national level quantitative data will not provide the detailed insights required to understand a vulnerable communities' information needs and any concerns and barriers that may prevent them from following protective measures. To address this, the COVINFORM risk assessment dashboard combines both quantitative data at the national level with qualitative interview data collected at the local level across ten case study sites in WP3 (Figure 1). The qualitative data covers:

- ➔ The characteristics of the study population in each case study
- ➔ The different factors which make these groups more vulnerable to COVID-19

Figure 1. COVINFORM risk assessment dashboard: Case Study Overview (Mock-up version)

The inclusion of this qualitative data in the dashboard provides complementary contextual insights that enables a deeper understanding and explanation of the quantitative data at a national level. For instance, whilst the quantitative data may show a high level of information vulnerability, it is the qualitative data, as demonstrated by the quote below, that provides the context in which it makes people and particular groups more vulnerable:

“It is hard to learn a language when you live alone and have to stay at home every day, not talking to other people, especially as I have no internet at home and no laptop.”
 (Case Study: ‘Migrant communities in Borgerhout and Antwerpen Noord, Belgium’)

Recommendation from WP2

Combine quantitative and qualitative data to gain a holistic understanding of vulnerability and information needs. While national level quantitative data can provide high-level insights for further exploration, qualitative data collected at a local level can offer rich insights to understand the information needs of vulnerable groups and any concerns and barriers that may prevent them from following protective measures.

Relevant deliverables:

- [COVINFORM D2.1 Database containing different data sources](#)
- [COVINFORM D2.3 Technical Report](#)
- [COVINFORM D2.4 Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers](#)

WP3: COVINFORM CASE STUDY EVALUATIONS: SPOTLIGHT ON COMMUNICATION VULNERABILITIES IN ETHNIC MINORITY GROUPS IN ENGLAND

WP3 focuses on the COVINFORM project’s design and evaluation of case-study research, which aims to identify promising practices in vulnerable communities. Early in the project, COVINFORM partners defined 15 target communities for in-depth desk-based research. Target communities were determined on the basis of scientific interest and partner access. From these 15 communities, 10 case studies were then selected for empirical research. The case studies explore vulnerabilities at a local level (municipality, region, etc.) with specific target populations (healthcare professionals, migrants, etc.), to better understand their lived experiences of COVID-19 (e.g., impacts and the ability to overcome challenges).

Exploring communication vulnerabilities was the primary objective for many partners. Media Diversity Institute and Trilateral Research aimed to better understand the local case study of England (West Midlands), how communication was experienced in hard-to-reach communities (ethnic and religious minorities) and to examine the extent to which the official government and health authorities’ COVID-19 messages reached members of minority groups. The main objective of the case study is the identification of alternative communication practices developed within these communities as a response and adjustment to the pandemic.

A total of 31 interviews were conducted and analysis of the case study findings are ongoing. Below are some preliminary findings, which will further be elaborated on in deliverable D3.8, “Final case study reports and comparative report – update” due in M35 (September 2023).

Key lessons learned relating to communication identified from the interviews include:

Misinformation

One interviewee commented that during the vaccination drive, there was a lot of misinformation, particularly within ethnic groups. The interviewee reported that they felt it was important for medics, doctors and professionals specialising in vaccination to approach ethnic communities and explain the vaccines carefully. The interviewee explained:

“As I said, even during the vaccination drive, there was a lot of misinformation, particularly within the ethnic groups, about what this vaccination is about, what does the vaccine contain, or whether we should go for it, whether we should not. I believe that was another key moment where we had to make sure our medics, our doctors, professionals within that particular field, came up and explained to the community that what is this about.”

Another interviewee commented that misinformation was fought by reaching out to professionals for advice, and then communicating with specific groups about the safety of the vaccine.

Representation

The interviewee findings revealed that their shared identities helped with the communication of COVID-19 information to their target audience. For example, one interviewee explained that when she wore a Sari, a women's garment from the Indian subcontinent, this helped with the distribution of key messages to the community. The interviewee commented:

“Again, I realised it was important they could relate to me. I wore a sari, for example, which I think is really important if you're getting these key messages out to the community.”

Alternative communication channels

When communicating COVID-19 information, the interviews revealed that a range of communication channels were used to educate the public about the pandemic. For example, one interviewee disclosed that they did some work on radio talking in Gujarati addressing the local Indian radio stations in and around England, talking about the COVID-19 vaccine, and putting the government's messages in languages that were understandable. Furthermore, another interviewee explained that as a member of the Leicester Council of Faiths, they would translate messages coming from the National Health Service into their own languages. Then, they would make short videos and short messages, which would then be sent to communities via social media platforms.

Recommendations from WP3

Upon reflection of the WP3 interviews, recommendations include:

Working on strategies to overcome misinformation, which include advice from trusted professionals, representation from minority groups to gain and build trust, and using alternative communication channels where the audience includes hard to reach community members.

Relevant deliverables:

- [COVINFORM D3.1 Case Study Selection](#)
- [COVINFORM D3.4 Case Study Reports and Comparative Report](#)

WP4: GOVERNMENT COVID-19 COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES

For the COVINFORM project, WP4 focuses on government responses to the COVID-19 pandemic.

This WP explored the different communication strategies implemented by the COVINFORM countries under study for WP4: Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom (England and Wales). The exploration of communication for WP4 is particularly important as government actors generally provided updates at a national level during the crisis, and how well a government communicates during a crisis has a direct impact on public trust, compliance, and support from the public (Sanchez, 2020).

Besides secondary research, WP4 has involved interviews with relevant stakeholders. Thus far, 57 interviews have been carried out across the COVINFORM countries.

Key lessons learned relating to WP4 communication includes:

- Most of the COVINFORM target countries under study for WP4 opted for centralised communication strategies. Strategies predominantly consisted of communications via official websites and regular press conferences, usually led by well-known Epidemiologists, Prime Ministers, Ministers, and appropriate governmental agents, particularly from the Ministry of Health. In this project, it has been reported that the success of the communication strategies rested on the actors involved in the communication and the level of public trust in the actors communicating COVID-19 information.
- Apart from the official government websites, dedicated COVID-19 official websites and social media that contained all measures and relevant information on COVID-19 evolution were adopted. In addition, specific thematic and targeted campaigns were created. The campaigns touched on hygiene measures, social distancing practices, vaccination plan and procedures, the protection of certain vulnerable populations, and counteracts to misinformation
- It was identified that consistency, transparency, and timing of information dissemination were the factors that contributed to the success rate of communication in each country.
- Communication efforts that focused on vulnerable populations initially lacked a tailored approach. However, communication towards such populations became more structured towards the later phases of the COVID-19 pandemic. Attention was paid to vulnerable populations because of their increased needs, which mainly comprised of conveying information in different languages and sign language. Targeted campaigns also included visualisations and videos to address the needs of illiterate citizens.

Recommendations from WP4

Collaborative communication structures should be in place preceding future (health) crises. These structures must prioritise their ability to respond to quickly evolving emergencies and crisis sensitivities. The incorporation of scientific evidence into political decision-making can strengthen policy initiatives and public trust.

Pre-existing communication structures and plans should include developed strategies that focus on reaching vulnerable groups. To reach vulnerable groups effectively, there should be a commitment to advance targeted and tailored communication that teach, inform, and stimulate protective behaviours, strengthen trust in the source, and eliminate myths.

Relevant deliverables:

- [COVINFORM 4.1 Baseline Report Governmental Responses](#)
- [COVINFORM 4.3 Analysis Government Responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment](#)
- [COVINFORM 4.4 Synthesis and Lessons Learnt on Governmental responses and impacts](#)

WP5: PUBLIC HEALTH MESSAGING DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

WP5 focuses on public health responses to the COVID-19 pandemic. The WP explored the COVID-19 impact and response from a public health perspective, with a specific focus on health inequality and vulnerability. Various communication and information strategies were implemented by public health experts to inform the public about COVID-19, the risks and benefits of specific actions, policies, and measures. And in the latter stages, public health messaging focused on COVID-19 vaccination. Researchers investigating COVID-19 communications during the pandemic have revealed that public health messaging has influenced public compliance (McCloughlin et al, 2023). They reported that effective health messaging offers manageable instructions, which influence public confidence that adhering to COVID-19 advice is worthwhile (ibid). As stated by researchers Robb Butler and Noni E MacDonald, poor public health communication can “cause confusion, scepticism, and resistance in the population, which may negatively impact the implementation of immunization programs.” (Butler & MacDonald, 2015). The COVINFORM project partners identified key lessons from their desktop-based research and interviews with public health experts and healthcare professionals. Note that the interviews cover public health communication. For the first iteration of analysis of WP5 interviews, 15 health care workers’ interviews were analysed and synthesised (the analysis of outstanding interviews completed is ongoing).

Key lessons learned relating to communication identified from the research include:

- Public health actors played an important role in COVID-19 specific communication and information strategies. However, there was significant variation across countries in the degree to which public health actors took centre stage in communicating about the pandemic. In all countries, it was identified that public health officials with training in fields like epidemiology and virology were tasked with communicating about the epidemiological situation, providing updates on figures such as COVID-19 case numbers and hospitalization rates.
- As vaccination campaigns were rolled out, these were accompanied by specific communication efforts to inform the public about COVID-19 vaccines. Examples include the Österreich impft (Austria vaccinates) campaign by the Austrian Red Cross, and the RO Vaccinare (Rovaccinate) campaign by the Romanian government. Österreich impft featured a website as well as campaigns in traditional and social media. RO Vaccinare is a Facebook page run by the Romanian government. Regarding the RO Vaccinare campaign, good practices include adopting a different method from the standard messages urging vaccination (Obreja, 2022). One strategy of the RO Vaccinare campaign included revealing the alternative narratives that vaccinated individuals bring into discussion (ibid). Exposure to positive messaging was said to heighten the probabilities of persuading people to get vaccinated (ibid).

- Interviewees reported that the sheer quantity of frequently changing evidence led to information overload, which was hard for people to deal with.
- Communication with ‘vulnerable groups’ around vaccination involved translating the latest COVID-19 guidance to a range of different languages, as well as making materials available in sign language and ‘simple language.’

Recommendations from WP5

- Public health communication needs careful planning to avoid the undermining of public participation and compliance. Emergency, and reactive communication should be replaced by strategic communication involving all relevant stakeholders. To this end, preventive plans, and communication drills should be carried out to develop future crisis scenarios and increase citizenship participation. Note that a drill is *“a method of learning or training where you do something over and over again until you are very familiar with it and can do it well and easily.”*¹
- To overcome confusion around changing evidence and feelings of information fatigue, pre-existing preparedness plans should be developed to strengthen good practices. A developed plan should also include effective public health responses to consider for future pandemics.
- Attention should be paid to addressing the concerns of vulnerable groups. With a particular focus on refugees and migrants, information should be translated and then disseminated through efficient channels including NGOs, refugee or migrant volunteers, and respective communities (ibid).
- Public surveys could help identify failures, scope, and drawbacks of the communication strategies to improve and plan future actions in the field of public health.

Relevant deliverables:

- [COVINFORM D5.1 Baseline Report on Public Health Responses](#)
- [COVINFORM D5.3 Analysis Public Health Responses and Impact](#)
- [COVINFORM D5.4 Synthesis and Lessons Learnt on Public Health Responses and Impacts](#)

¹ Scientology. (N.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.scientologycourses.org/tools-for-life/communication/steps/communication-training-drills.html>

WP6: COMMUNITY LEVEL COVID-19 COMMUNICATION

COVINFORM also examines the COVID-19 impact and response at the “community” level in WP6. This includes analysing different community structures and stakeholder networks, the local implementation and impacts of governmental pandemic responses, and voluntary and citizen-led responses to the pandemic.

Focusing on the community level impact and response to COVID-19 is important as the measures implemented did not impact all groups equally. For example, communication gaps during the pandemic disproportionately impacted vulnerable groups (Clark-Ginsberg & Petrun Sayers, 2020). This has been suggested to be due to a lack of access to technology and high-speed internet that reduces access to particular communication channels, decreased confidence and mistrust of authorities, and the spread of misinformation (ibid.).

For WP6, COVINFORM partners conducted a combination of desk-based and primary research at the community level to understand the COVID-19 impact and response, and promising practices for policy co-production or co-implementation. The primary research comprises 38 qualitative interviews, and continues to enrol participants, across sub-national sites in nine countries.

Key lessons learned relating to communication identified from the research include:

- Community led approaches to communicating COVID-19 information to vulnerable groups involved a variety of different stakeholders (e.g., key community figures, religious institutions, and stakeholders, NGOs/CSOs, and socio-cultural organizations). These stakeholders were involved in launching and/or participating in different practices to promote COVID-19 information by translating, adapting, and/or disseminating official information to their networks. Examples of practices identified include:

1. The City of Antwerp, Belgium, recruited people with a broad network in their neighbourhood, religious community, or migrant community as ‘Sensi Ambassadors’. The Sensi Ambassadors received training about COVID-19, distributed multilingual communication materials, and acted as a trusted source of information for their network.
2. Birmingham City Council, UK, launched a [*“COVID-19 Community Champions”*](#) initiative whereby people aged over 18 years old who live or work in Birmingham were able to volunteer to share COVID-19 guidance and advice with their networks, family, and friends. As of 16th March 2021, Birmingham had 766 Community Champions.

- Most interviewees highlighted their target groups as vulnerable to disinformation and misinformation and highlighted the need for more effective ways to counter these threats.
- Cooperative, synergistic, and/or complementary actions by Governmental Organisations and NGOs/CSOs were associated with positive outcomes and were widely praised as good practices.

Recommendations from WP6

- Governmental organisations should collaborate with CSOs to adapt risk communication messages into forms that their target groups can understand. CSOs can act as bridging organisations to communities.
- Enable proactive cooperation between governmental risk communicators and CSOs and representatives of vulnerable groups to debunk myths.
- Information exchange should be bidirectional and include opportunities for communities to be heard.

Relevant deliverables:

- [COVINFORM D6.1 Baseline report Community and citizen responses](#)
- [COVINFORM D6.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts](#)

WP7: INCLUSIVE COVID-19 COMMUNICATION FOR BEHAVIOUR CHANGE AND ADDRESSING MISINFORMATION

As communication has played a key role in the response to COVID-19, COVINFORM WP7 is dedicated to inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation.

People’s behaviour has been key to the COVID-19 response during the different stages of the pandemic including both the adoption of protective measures (e.g., physical distancing) and vaccination. In the early stages of the pandemic, policies focused on national and regional communication of public health measures due to the absence of a vaccination and approved treatments (Fakhruddin, Blanchard, & Ragupathy 2020). However, the pandemic did not only involve the communication of protective measures but also saw the spread of false information. This included misinformation (unintentionally false information) and disinformation (false information purposely spread (Lazer et al., 2018)). In response to the overwhelming information, including mis- and disinformation, the World Health Organization categorised COVID-19 as an ‘infodemic’ (WHO, 2020).

For WP7, partners conducted desk-based and primary research to identify and analyse the communication practices used, main lessons, and best practices across the COVINFORM partner countries. The findings and recommendations presented below are based on the findings of the desk-based research across 15 countries as the data from the primary research is currently being analysed. Thirty-eight interviews have been conducted thus far, and the interview findings will be presented in D7.7, “Analysis Communication and Information – update” due in M34 (August 2023).

Key lessons learned relating to communication identified from the desk-based research include:

- Inconsistencies and conflicting messages were common in almost all of the countries analysed. This included unclear messages, contradictions, disagreements between politicians or between politicians and experts, and/or erroneous claims that all caused confusion and uncertainty.
- Trust and transparency both play a key role in communication. In some countries, there was already a lack of trust in official (government) communication, while in others, a perceived lack of transparency may have caused a decline in trust.
- Risk communication followed a multi-channel strategy, which increases the reach of the messages, across all the countries under research. However, COVID-19 communication was predominantly one-way and top-down approach with all countries using press conferences, (government-run) websites and dashboards, as well as mass media (TV, radio, as well as printed and online newspapers).

- Government communication mainly appeared to target the general public, however, official communication in most countries did also address certain vulnerable groups, at least to some degree. This included targeted communication to: those affected by language and/or cultural barriers; older people; children and young people; people living with disabilities; people living with health vulnerabilities; and healthcare workers.
- Close relationships between the government and various NGOs and CSOs were identified in some countries with NGOs and CSOs playing an important role in shaping and/or amplifying risk communication and tailoring communication to different vulnerable groups.

Recommendations from WP7

- Two-way communication channels (e.g., hotlines) should be used to engage with the target audience and gain insights into their perceptions, information needs, and the impact of the communication. This will foster inclusivity which is particularly crucial for effective communication of information to vulnerable groups, those who may be at increased risk of harm, such as the socioeconomically disadvantaged, and ethnic and linguistic minorities, among others (Anson et al., 2021, b).
- Identify sources (e.g., religious or community leaders) that are credible to different target audiences to share messages (Bavel et al. 2020) as trusted and credible communication is essential for effective risk communication.
- Information should be reliable and grounded in scientific evidence. For instance, messaging regarding personal mitigation measures such as wearing facemasks and social distancing should be accompanied by information regarding their scientific basis.
- Research should be conducted to understand the support systems available such as civil society organisations (e.g., community centres, faith-based institutions) that provide alternative information sources for vulnerable groups. This research should also consider the capacity that CSOs and NGOs have for tailoring, shaping, and amplifying communication to different vulnerable groups.

Relevant deliverables:

- [COVIFORM D7.1 Baseline report Communication and information](#)
- [COVIFORM D7.4 Synthesis and Lessons Learned on Communication, Information and Misinformation](#)
- Anson, S., Bertel, D., Havârneanu G., & Petersen, L. (2021). [Inclusive communication in times of crisis: lessons learned and recommendations from COVID-19 and other CBRNe incidents based on recent COVIFORM & PROACTIVE findings](#). Whitepaper. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27104.97286

WP8: AN OVERVIEW OF PRE-EXISTING BI-MONTHLY REPORTS COVERING COMMUNICATION DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

WP8 aims to create reports and materials for stakeholders and to develop recommendations and best practices to influence adherence to behavioural advice across different groups in society. In particular, the objective of task 8.1 (coordinated by Sapienza University of Rome (SAPIENZA)) is to create and publish useful output of the project every two months in the form of brief reports, snippets, webinars, etc. for the different stakeholders. The task started in month three of the project, with the first report published in January 2021, and the final report to be published in September 2023. To date, four reports have touched on communication during the COVID-19 pandemic. The relevant reports are as follows:

[*COVID-19 Vaccines: History and Facts – Bi-Monthly Report: 01*](#)

This report opens with a brief review of the history of vaccines, and then describes the current (as of January 2021) situation regarding COVID-19 vaccines, also exploring the issue of misinformation related to these types of vaccines. Since misinformation falls under communication, readers can turn to page 10 of the report to learn more about how this practice evolved during the COVID-19 pandemic.

[*A Glimpse of the Lessons Learned During the COVID-19 Pandemic – Bi-Monthly Report: 03*](#)

In this report, the global methods for communication during the COVID-19 pandemic are discussed. Lessons learned from the communication vehicles are witnessed, leading to best practices and guidelines for improved communication in the future.

[*COVID-19: Findings on the Governmental Responses in COVINFORM countries – Bi-Monthly Report: 04*](#)

This bi-monthly report summarises the findings of the desk-based research that was conducted for the purposes of WP4 in the COVINFORM project. An overall view of the institutional and governmental responses in the 14 target countries have been provided in conjunction with several visuals. For further information on communication practices, please refer to page 13.

[*Viruses of the mind. Coping and joking about COVID-19 – Bi-Monthly Report: 07*](#)

This report presents outcomes of an explorative analysis of memes conducted in the context of the COVINFORM project. The aim of this report is to gain an understanding of how humour was used to cope with the events of the pandemic and communicate with others, to share specific narratives, and to comment on experiences during the pandemic.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, this bi-monthly report has demonstrated the significance of communication across all the different WPs under study. Following the evaluation of pre-existing COVINFORM deliverables containing both desk-top based research and interviews with relevant stakeholders, a number of lessons learned stood out:

- For WP2, both quantitative and qualitative data/insights can help with the identification and understanding of communication vulnerabilities. This includes varying degrees of digital skills and the need to use traditional communication channels to reach different groups.
- For WP3, misinformation, representation, and alternative communication channels were examples of topics that interviewees touched on when addressing communication among vulnerable groups.
- For WP4, the actors involved and the level of public trust in communicators contributed towards the level of success of government communication strategies.
- For WP5, health officials in fields like virology and epidemiology played an important role in communicating public health messages.
- For WP6, community-led approaches focused heavily on supporting vulnerable groups. Support came in the form of translating, adapting, and disseminating official information to networks.
- For WP7, close relationships between government and various NGOs and CSOs were identified in some countries, with NGOs and CSOs paying an important role in shaping and/or amplifying risk communication.
- For WP8, the lessons learned from WP2-7 will be summarised in policy briefs, white papers, and fact sheets.

Finally, the recommendations presented in this report have presented an opportunity for strengthened communication practices, which ought to be acted on should another pandemic breakout in the future. Common recommendation trends across all the WPs include strengthened collaboration between appropriate bodies, careful policy planning, consistent and clear messaging, and understanding the needs of all vulnerable groups.

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The COVINFORM project

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**Migrant women
during the
pandemic: multiple
and intertwined
vulnerabilities**

Bi-Monthly Report: 17

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INTRODUCTION

This bi-monthly report is directly linked to the citizen interviews conducted for Work Packages 4 to 7 of COVINFORM, which focuses on analysing citizen and community responses and the impact of COVID-19. In particular, the focus of qualitative fieldwork implemented within the project was to understand the gendered impacts of the pandemic by interviewing a sample of women with low socioeconomic status (SES). This group was chosen because low socioeconomic status consistently emerged as a risk factor across different countries, allowing for meaningful cross-country comparisons. The primary focus of the fieldwork was to investigate how women with low SES obtained information and formal/informal support during the pandemic.

The fieldwork on women with low SES is based on COVINFORM's intersectional theoretical framework and employs social network analysis to examine patterns of relationships and resource exchange among individuals, organizations, or institutions. These resources can be tangible (like money, services, or goods) or intangible (such as friendships, social support, and information). Social networks play a crucial role in determining access to influence and power, as they facilitate the flow of resources and information at various levels (household, community, or institutional), leading to diverse experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic. The analysis of the transcripts of these interviews contributes to improving the understanding of how people can mitigate disadvantages and highlights that groups with shared characteristics (e.g., gender, socioeconomic status, migrant status) are not homogeneous.

In the fieldwork implementation, each project partner compiled a list of Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) operating within their designated sub-national research area, usually cities, with women with low socioeconomic status. Consequently, several partners aimed to engage with at least one CSO that assists this population group. Furthermore, it was established that a minimum of 12 interviews should be conducted per research site.

The semi-structured interviews were guided by a framework developed by COVINFORM's Consortium researchers. This interview approach centers on the broad theme of experiences during the period from the start of the pandemic in 2020 to July 2022 when the interviews were conducted. The semi-structured nature of the interviews allows for flexibility as the conversation unfolds, and it is organized in seven main topic areas.

1. A warm-up question;
2. Key memories of pandemic: the most important memories of the pandemic;
3. Social networks: how face-to-face contacts changed;
4. Support networks: any kind of support received during that time;
5. Information seeking and sense-making: how and where the respondent inquired about the virus, measures, testing, vaccines...;
6. Living Environment: how the place where the respondent lives played a role in the experience of the COVID-19 pandemic;
7. Closing question.

The resident interview guide developed within the WP4-7 highlights the novelty of this questionnaire, which aims to gather innovative data on topics not previously well-documented. Traditionally, vulnerability has been linked to ascribed status rather than a genuine lived experience. By focusing on a group often categorized as vulnerable, this study explores the disparities between assigned vulnerability and the actual experiences people undergo.

This analysis is particularly pertinent for gaining insights into the lives of women with low socioeconomic status (SES). Poverty frequently results in social exclusion and isolation, especially when considering women who also belong to another disadvantaged category, such as migrants. Socioeconomically disadvantaged individuals tend to have limited social networks and support systems, which restricts their access to information and practical assistance.

During the pandemic, lockdowns and social distancing measures exacerbated the isolation experienced by some individuals, even though there was a greater need for social support due to added stress factors related to finances, health, and well-being. The research outcomes could be valuable for policymakers in improving the quality of support networks and enhancing information access for more marginalized groups.

This bi-monthly report is based on the above-mentioned qualitative research conducted in several research sites: Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Spain, and Sweden. We gathered data from 76 women who were interviewed in these countries, 52 of them being migrants.

MAIN FINDINGS

The interviews conducted explore the lived experiences of migrant women during the pandemic. Within those interviews, the topics covered include the composition of their households, their occupational status, their social and support network, and their information-seeking habits.

The icebreaker used to start these interviews asked interviewees to recall three significant memories of the pandemic. Responses mostly evoke the lockdown period: their whereabouts when it was enacted in the different countries, how they spent lockdowns... Narratives also recall many negative feelings experienced during this period: the fear of contagion, uncertainty regarding the duration of the pandemic or the anxiety of job loss and food insecurity. However, there were also spaces for more positive feelings and some respondents recall bonding with their families and looking for ways to cheer up those around them.

The effects of the pandemic have exacerbated social inequalities. In line with recent literature, data collected on this study show that migrants' occupational status was marked by a paradox. They were more likely to occupy positions included in the list of essential workers, and at the same time, they experienced more precarity than other social groups. Their occupational profiles often include low-skilled work like domestic workers, cleaners, cashiers, etc. In countries with a high prevalence of the informal economy, job insecurity was further aggravated because these respondents were often not eligible for income substitution schemes. Or if they were, only for a partial substitution, as their work in the informal economy was not declared and, therefore, not computed in the income loss of the family. The combination of these factors not only created food insecurity amongst many of

the migrants interviewed, but it also impacted the economies of the countries of origin, as they could not send the remittances their families rely on.

In terms of their living conditions, the migrants that we interview did not complain much about their living conditions. Nonetheless, amongst the interviewees there is a wide variety in terms of housing arrangements. Some live in shared flats, while others have their own apartments. However, one complaint we heard multiple times was the lack of outdoor spaces within the house or the impossibility of going outside, specially amongst respondents with young children. A particular case is found in Rome, where more than 60 families shared outdoor spaces where they could step out during the lockdown and stay in touch with neighbors. These women felt lucky as they could take advantage of the closeness of others, despite the risk of contagion.

In the countries where they currently live, migrants have worked hard to build new social networks. The density of these networks varies across respondents, as some have engaged in more active social activities and others have focused on working and maximizing income to be able to send remittances to their families in their countries of origin. Amongst those who are more active, they have built those networks over friendship, local associations, and religious communities. When the COVID pandemic struck, these networks suffered a blow, and many respondents describe the loss of these relationships.

Despite the disruption that these associations and religious communities suffered, they proved to be crucial to many of the people interviewed. Governments across countries passed different measures directed to provide income support and

buffer the sudden breaking of economic activity caused by the lockdowns. Migrants were often excluded from these measures or insufficiently covered. Irregularities in their administrative status or the reliance in the informal economy hindered their applications to furlough schemes or equivalent programs. Thus, families that had been able to make ends meet found themselves suddenly applying for social aid. This sudden increase of the demand for social services combined with the lack of protective protocols, created significant difficulties for institutions across many of the countries where the interviews were conducted. The interviewees recall turning to CSOs and religious communities for help. These organizations were crucial as they attracted additional funding to respond these new demands. They also connected individuals, which allowed them to redistribute social aid and maximize the coverage of the help provided.

In terms of information seeking and sense-making, institutional sources broadcast on television were one of the favorite communication channels. Migrants combined this information with Internet

searches, information circulating in private social networks (i.e.: WhatsApp groups) and YouTube channels that provided information in their mother tongue, helped them understand what they did not understand in the national language of their host country and gather information about the situation in their countries of origin. Religious beliefs also played a role in sense-making and religious communities developed different strategies to maintain the connection with members (broadcasting religious services, Zoom groups, etc.).

Respondents did not feel they believed any piece of information that was false, they did acknowledge that they received questionable information through social media or YouTube. Many of the interviewees underline that, although they were overall happy with the quality of the information provided, they find it would have been useful to tailor the information to specific target groups and to provide it in a wider variety of languages. In Austria, mailing informative letters was positively perceived.

CONCLUSION

- The theoretical framework combined intersectionality with a complex systems approach. Although this report focuses on citizens' interviews, the outputs of the project contextualize these interviews with the institutional practices and the interventions promoted by CSOs. Regarding the interviews, the main implication is that the interviews step out of a logic where migrants are a vulnerable community, instead what the interviews suggest is that migrants faced multiple and intertwined vulnerabilities.
- Migrant women found themselves in complex situations characterized by the fear of contagion, high risk of job loss and food insecurity, anxiety due to the uncertainty of the duration of this crisis and solitude.
- Higher contagion risks were linked to their socioeconomic status rather than to the prevalence of pre-existing co-morbidities. Overall, these interviewees were healthy and declared few pre-existing ailments. However, they often worked in essential but poorly valued occupations like care-providers or cashiers. These occupations experienced higher risks of contagion as they could not work from home and had to commute.
- Future crises should encourage strategies to enhance social interconnectedness, as it proved very effective in the redistribution and maximization of social aid.
- The interviews suggest that solitude was linked to the inability to visit and stay in close contact with family and friends. However, in this regard there is quite some heterogeneity, as those with more dense social networks quickly turned to videocalls and social networks to make up, at least partially, for the inability to meet others.
- Regarding information patterns, migrants consumed information from official channels and informal channels was positively evaluated. However, there seems to be room for improvement in terms of clarity and dealing with uncertainty, targeting of information, languages in which it was made available, and the channels used to spread information.
- Finally, the recommendations presented in this report have presented an opportunity for strengthened communication practices, which ought to be acted on should another pandemic breakout in the future. Common recommendation trends across all the WPs include strengthened collaboration between appropriate bodies, careful policy planning, consistent and clear messaging, and understanding the needs of all vulnerable groups.

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COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**How
to build and
how to lose trust.
Lessons learned and
resident perspectives on
crisis communication.**

Bi-Monthly Report: 18

Authors

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INTRODUCTION

Trust is a fragile yet vital component of society, especially during times of crisis. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the importance of trust in governments, in science and (independent) media. A well-developed crisis communication management is crucial to create meaningful impact through crisis communication. Here too, trust is crucial, particularly in relation to adherence to public health advice. There are many factors that can lead to successful crisis communication such as a well thought out crisis communication plan, the distribution of responsibilities, the handling of false- and misinformation, the way crisis communication is put into practice and how different segments of society are reached.

Work package 7 of the COVINFORM project is concerned with the COVID-19 pandemic response on communication and information, particularly in relation to vulnerable groups. In our deliverables (D7.1- D7.8) as well as other outputs such as our whitepaper (see Covinform.eu) we have discussed good and bad communication practices as well as lessons learned and recommendations from the past three years. This bi-monthly report focuses on COVID-19 communication and trust with a focus on the experiences and perceptions of vulnerable groups. The aim is to illustrate the voices of vulnerable groups, in particular, of women of low socioeconomic background in Austria, Belgium, England, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and Wales. We use these experiences and perceptions to highlight the lessons learned and

recommendations that we identified through our desk-based research and expert interviews (see D7.8, WP7 whitepaper). Additionally, they highlight that our interlocutors are not a homogenous group and trust is relational, contextual and situational. The purpose of this report is to show a different side of this crisis and highlight the experience of those who carried the disproportionate load of the pandemic consequences.

The COVINFORM project interviewed 120 women of low socioeconomic status (in each country 12 women). We recruited them through civil society organisations (CSO) and governmental organisations providing financial and material support. We conducted semi-narrative, semi-problem focused interviews which lasted between 20-60 minutes each. The interviews were tape recorded, transcribed and translated into English. The aim was to understand the lived experiences of people who are affected by multiple forms of disadvantage. Prior to this the COVINFORM project conducted in-depth country analysis drawing on secondary sources and interviews with experts (20 experts in each country) in each of the ten countries.

HOW DID VULNERABLE GROUPS PERCEIVE COVID-19 CRISIS COMMUNICATION

Reasons for trust in authorities and media as well as reasons for the erosion of trust over time, were diverse. For example, mistrust was created through contradictory messages, instrumentalising the pandemic for political aims, dishonesty of politicians, exaggeration of information instigating fear, lack of information or an oversaturation with information, everchanging information as well as rules and regulations without guidance on how to navigate these changes. Trust, however, was created through consistency, transparency and through a good rapport with people that were considered trustworthy including the government. However, this level of trust already needed to be there prior to the pandemic. In D7.8 and our whitepaper ‘Inclusive communication in times of crisis’ we identified a few key points that led to a decrease of trust as well as crisis communication rules that foster trust particularly when communicating with vulnerable groups.

Factors that could lead to mistrust:

- Political scandals, changes in the government, inconsistency in governmental rules and regulations including often changing measures as well as sudden changes in political strategies regarding the pandemic
- The involvement of too many actors in the crisis communication who send contradictory messages as well as a lack of coordination between state institutions
- An undifferentiated one-size-fits-all communication approach. Such an approach may be insufficient in addressing the diverse needs of the public and result in mistrust among certain groups.
- Negative, one-sided or sensational reporting about the pandemic often led to unnecessary panic and fear among the public and further created mistrust.
- A lack of scientific journalists who could explain the scientific aspects of the pandemic in an accurate and understandable way.

We identified a few factors leading to positive outcomes and trust:

- Actionable communication and setting clear expectations what residents should do
- Providing understandable scientific and statistical evidence
- Providing transparency by being consistent and explaining the motives behind certain decisions and messages
- Aiming for understandable and inclusive communication tailored to the specific needs of certain groups
- Prioritising timely and relevant information to minimise the risk of overwhelming the audience

The selected quotes below reflect on these lessons learned and recommendations and substantiate those with the voices of the vulnerable groups we interviewed to present the residents' perspective to our findings of WP7. Additionally, they highlight that our interlocutors are not a homogenous group and trust is relational, contextual and situational.

Trust in official COVID-19 communication from a resident's perspective

In general, the women we interviewed had trust in the information communicated by governments, media and health experts. One of the findings of our interviews was that our interlocutors, in many instances, talked interchangeably about trust in government, media and science. A reason might have been that people may have conflated the messages sent by the government via the media with the media itself. This conflation needs to be kept in mind when interpreting the statements of the women in relation to their trust to the media. Finally, the women we interviewed also expressed trust in social workers, friends, family members and their gut feeling.

There was a general sense that governments, and even more so public health authorities could be trusted, even if not all would agree to this statement.

I: And did you trust the information?

R: Yes, from the government I did. (Resident 3 Belgium)

R: I usually consulted pages of the national health system. (Resident 3 Portugal)

As one woman from England explained, the official state homepages felt safe in terms of finding reliable information particularly in comparison to information she could find on social media.

I felt like with the NHS and the government website, they would provide the most accurate information. Whereas, if I was to look online, or even social platforms, not a lot of them - they wouldn't give you what you needed, and often exaggerate things. So I was actually avoiding those kinds of platforms. (Resident 2 England)

One resident also explicitly mentioned a municipal authority as a good and trustworthy source of information, while others only stated to trust information disseminated by the government. Interestingly most interlocutors did not give a reason why they would trust state authorities.

We decided that the only source of reliable information was what the mayor said. And when he wrote there that we can get together, well, we get together. If he says that we can't get together yet, then no. If he says we can go to the social club, then we go. (Resident 5 Spain)

Particularly in the German interviews that we conducted we could observe that trust in scientists was higher. In particular, Christian Drosten from the Charité in Berlin in Germany or Karl Lauterbach, a German politician with a professional background in medicine.

I: How do you decide that, that's a difficult thing. How do you decide what information you trust?

R: Well, I want to say the virologists and the scientists and so, I think they're saying so largely the right thing. (Resident 8 Germany)

Trust in science, among some residents, also extended to medical personnel such as general practitioners – especially in regard to the vaccination:

I only trust my doctors and filtered everything [out] that we were told by non-experts with no medical background. (Resident 12 Greece)

Another category of trusted sources is built through social networks such as social workers, family and friends

[...] Or the manager of the house [social worker]. If he said something, that was also a matter for me, yes. Because he is a very thoughtful person and you can believe what he says. 100 percent. (Resident Austria 4)

Finally, we could observe that our interlocutors told us that they trusted their friends and their gut feeling. This was often a reaction to being overwhelmed by the information provided by media, social media and officials.

[...] The information, the first information, above all from friends, from people you know and people you know who know about the subject. With all these things that I've told you about the concealment of facts and things that didn't add up for me every time. I trusted less what was said on TV, more than anything else because you could also see something completely different on the street. Therefore, I paid more attention to the people we understood and who were friends. (Resident 3 Spain)

Mistrust in official COVID-19 communication from a resident's perspective

As already mentioned, some residents seemed not to fully trust politicians in general. This was also reflected in their lack of trust during the pandemic.

I believe that we are in the hands of politicians, that we have to act according to what they tell us and they are not always trustworthy. So, that means to me, well, we will do what they tell us and we will never know if they have interests behind all that they have told us. (Resident 6 Spain)

In some cases, residents' mistrust is almost conspiratorial. Conspiratorial mistrust was in these cases, most likely already existent prior to the COVID-19 outbreak. However, the pandemic and its complexity may have reinforced these tendencies.

No, no. I didn't care and I don't care because they are all bullshit. This is a scientific war, it's a war that they have invented. They have taken the disease head-on to frighten the population. Because we are all scared, aren't we? We have prepared ourselves for the worst of what is happening to us, which is the increase in prices and all these things. It is the whole circle of politicians who have done this. (Resident 4 Italy)

The following quote illustrates how disappointment in politicians could have contributed, with time, to a loss of trust in government. As in many instances inconsistency in communication but also in action led to mistrust.

You know that time with Boris Johnson when he went on the - I think he had his party or - I don't know, that office party thing. For me that was kind of like, oh, how serious is this thing? Because obviously, you're telling us we need to stay home and do all of these things. But the same rules don't really apply to you. So is it as serious as you're telling us it is? Or have you got some other motive? So it wasn't - yeah, that didn't really feel - I didn't feel reassured about that, to be honest. I think that was the only time. (Resident 2 England)

What also factored into the rising mistrust against the governments' handling of the crisis were the constantly changing measures and rules to confine the spread of the virus. These changes elicited the feeling that the government itself did not know how to deal with the crisis or was having political motives behind their decisions. Additionally, it made it difficult to adhere to the rules as residents were confused about the timeliness.

There was a time when I didn't trust much of what they were saying, first they said that now everything had to be disinfected and then, suddenly, they said that it wasn't necessary. (Resident 6 Spain)

Changes in information often occurred due to new scientific insights. However, we have found that, in many countries, the official COVID-19 crisis communication did not succeed in guiding residents through these new information and respective changes to rules and regulations. This was particularly the case in relation to the vaccine. Although residents often received a lot of information, they did not know how to navigate it. For many an additional challenge was their irritation around how to engage with the continuously new information. Many felt lost and confused as expressed in the quote below.

And also they told, yeah, this vaccine works for this one, but for the next one it didn't work. It will not, or it doesn't or it didn't, also like uhm we don't know. Uhm, and then you kind of get your vaccination but you are still unprotected, or you are still protected or we don't know if you are protected. So, it was... and I think I do understand why there is a lot of scepticism about vaccines showing up because you know if you took three vaccines and you are still not protected you are asking like, excuse but for what I did this for, like explain to me. (Resident 1 Austria)

Our interlocutors also expressed mistrust towards the media. Interviewees assumed that the media exaggerated or manipulated information to control public opinion rather than serving as a reliable source of news. Some interviewees perceived that (political) motives might influence the information and decisions made by government officials and that the media was complicit. Moreover, multiple suspected ulterior motives behind pandemic-related information, perceiving it as a tool to manipulate public opinion and restrict freedom rather than a means to ensure public safety.

I tried not to give it too much importance, because behind the truth, the real numbers, there is a lot of speculation. You will never know the right number of infected, as well as the true action of vaccines. Let's just say there's a lot of people profiting from these kinds of situations. (Resident 3 Portugal)

In a similar manner, several interlocutors stated that, in their opinion, the media had exaggerated the crisis by unnecessarily instigating fear:

And also sometimes they exaggerate it by the tone of voice they give you. So, sometimes I used to say to my daughter, turn it off, let's see the main thing the president says, how much progress has been made, but I got tired of him saying so many deaths in such and such a department, so many deaths in so many provinces, I had it, my God, and that. (Resident 11 Spain)

Furthermore, in some instances, the residents we interviewed reported that this alarmism made them shy away from seeking and obtaining information on COVID-19 altogether:

I would avoid the news like a plague because I think I feel like it was ...it was tragic, but they overdramatize everything. I actually watched this funny video where this guy was saying how if the BBC I recording will always hear them talking in a certain tone, that always recording by a hospital that always tells you about deaths that always use the word tragic. And it was it was a funny video, but it was so relatable. And I avoided the news because I felt like it was just causing people anxiety. And it was just overdramatic. Like I'm not saying those things didn't happen. People didn't lose their lives. Of course they did. But the way they bought the news every single day, like it just was not called. I just feel like it made me feel worse. (Resident 2 Wales)

In other cases, they felt that they could not handle the sheer amount of bad and alarming news.

[...] we didn't want to check up. So it was quite a depressing time, so in the end you stopped caring a little about the information because it was so depressing. (Resident 7 Sweden)

In our interviews we could observe that our interlocutors also struggled with contradictory information. Interlocutors were exposed to different opinions and instructions that they have heard from various sources such as the government, the media and other channels they used to inform themselves including friends and families. It made it hard to know which information to trust and which to ignore.

Sometimes one writes like this, and then the other writes like that. And what are you supposed to believe there? (Resident 5 Austria)

No, that was so contradictory. One said that vaccination was absolutely necessary. The other said... then I read on the internet, of course, like everyone [did], you have to be careful with these drugs. So now you're standing there. (Resident 9 Austria)

We have seen that many of the points that we identified throughout our research such as political scandals, negative and sensational reporting, inconsistency or feeling of being overwhelmed by conflicting or too much information were also addressed by women of low socioeconomic background in the 10 COVINFORM countries. Of course, this is a very diverse sample even more so given that the women all lived in different countries. Nonetheless, it highlights commonalities and issues that occurred across Austria, Belgium, England, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and Wales. It also showed that the women we interviewed trusted in consistent and clear communication. Interesting was also the high trust in friends and families regardless of their actual knowledge on the given topic.

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3 Conclusions

The bi-monthly reports published in the second project period, had the aim to present the main findings of the project, both from the point of view of the desk and empirical research and from the point of view of the practitioners. Most of the bi-monthly reports were published in brochure format, with an appealing, schematic style and language that would capture the attention of the readers. The ninth and fifteenth reports were realized as video interviews. All the reports were realized with in mind a public of academics, policy makers at the governmental and local level, and CSOs. In several reports we involved directly the practitioners, in order to make these reports even more effective in their purpose.

The bi-monthly reports allow to contribute in a practical way to the knowledge and development of expertise and best practices for all those (workers, volunteers, scientists, policymakers, etc.) involved in activities related to the project topics and in the crisis management. Thanks to the smart and fast fruition of the project topics and main results, bi-monthly reports represent relevant instruments for the dissemination and for the transition from the project to the reality and actions.